

InBestSoil

Monetary valuation of soil ecosystem services and creation of initiatives to invest in soil health: setting a framework for the inclusion of soil health in business and in the policy making process- InBestSoil

D7.2 PRACTICE ABSTRACTS – BATCH 1

Practice Abstracts – Batch 1

Summary

This document represents Deliverable D7.2: **Practice Abstracts - Batch 1**, one of the outputs of Task 3.3: *Dissemination Strategy* within WP7 (*Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation*).

The main objective of **InBestSoil** is to co-create a framework for investing in the conservation and recovery of soil health. This involves developing an economic valuation system for the ecosystem services provided by healthy soils and assessing the impacts of soil interventions. The framework integrates these valuations into business models and incentive mechanisms, enabling public and private organizations to assign economic value to their actions regarding soil health. Additionally, it promotes co-design strategies with local stakeholders and collective efforts to achieve national and EU policy objectives.

InBestSoil aims to deliver data, evidence, tools, and models to evaluate how investments in soil health can support the transition to a resilient and sustainable long-term use of soils. The project employs 7 Lighthouses (LHs) and 2 Living Labs (LLs), covering 9 study areas across four biogeographic regions in Europe—Boreal, Continental, Atlantic, and Mediterranean—with diverse land uses such as agriculture, forestry, urban areas, and mining. These serve as models for co-creation and co-design, adopting a multi-actor approach, Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) principles, and open science practices.

WP7 focuses on ensuring efficient knowledge transfer through dissemination activities, multi-channel communication, participation in events, development of training materials, and the creation of strategies for long-term exploitation and sustainability.

This deliverable provides details of the first batch of Practice Abstracts produced by InBestSoil LHs and LLs. Each Practice Abstract translates scientific findings into practical, accessible formats, enabling the dissemination of results to the broader society.

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Introduction

In this document, we compile all 28 Practice Abstracts developed by the InBestSoil project partners. Each abstract has been prepared in English and translated into the native language of the corresponding study area, ensuring accessibility and facilitating knowledge transfer to local stakeholders and broader audiences.

The abstracts reflect the diversity of contexts addressed by the project, encompassing multiple biogeographic regions (Boreal, Continental, Atlantic, and Mediterranean) and various land uses such as agriculture, forestry, urban environments, and mining. The list of Practice Abstracts included in this first batch is presented, followed by the individual factsheets for each of them.

The project will continue to work on the creation of additional Practice Abstracts, with the goal of producing at least 100 abstracts by the end of the project (M48).

Table 1a. List of Practice Abstracts 1-7 (batch 1)

LH/LL	Practice Abstract	Title	Language
1	Practice Abstract 1	Enhancing soil health through rotational grazing in mediterranean forestry	EN
		Mejora de la calidad del suelo mediante el pastoreo rotacional en bosques Mediterráneos	ES
	Practice Abstract 2	Carbon pump: how cattle help to increase soil carbon storage	EN
		Bomba de carbono: aumento del almacenamiento de carbono en el suelo gracias al ganado	ES
	Practice Abstract 3	A management practice that improves soil and pasture productivity through controlled livestock impact	EN
		Práctica de manejo que mejora el suelo y la productividad de los pastos gracias al impacto controlado del ganado	ES
2	Practice Abstract 4	Enhancing soil health through the creation of artificial soils (Technosols) in tailing ponds.	EN
		Mejora de la salud del suelo mediante la creación de suelos artificiales (Tecnosoles) en depósitos de relaves mineros.	ES
	Practice Abstract 5	Reclamation of tailings pond using Technosols and phytostabilization leads to pollution reduction.	EN
		La rehabilitación de depósitos de relaves mineros mediante el uso de Tecnosuelos y fitoestabilización conduce a la reducción de la contaminación	ES
	Practice Abstract 6	Non-Market Value of ecosystem services associated with rehabilitated tailing ponds using technosols and phytostabilization	EN
		Valor de no mercado de los servicios ecosistémicos asociados a depósitos de relaves mineros rehabilitados mediante el uso de Tecnosuelos y fitoestabilización.	ES
	Practice Abstract 7	Reclamation of tailings pond using Technosols and phytostabilization increases soil microbial diversity and abundance	EN
		La rehabilitación de depósitos de relaves mineros mediante el uso de Tecnosuelos y fitoestabilización incrementa la abundancia y diversidad de microorganismos del suelo	ES

Table 1b. List of Practice Abstracts 8-16 (batch 1)

LH/LL	Practice Abstract	Title	Language
3	Practice Abstract 8	Restoration of degraded mining soils with Technosols: the mine of Touro	EN
		Restauración de suelos degradados con Tecnosoles: la mina de Touro	ES
	Practice Abstract 9	Reactive wetlands for the treatment of hyperacidic waters	EN
		Humedales reactivos para el tratamiento de aguas hiperácidas	ES
	Practice Abstract 10	Synergies between waste valorization and soil remediation	EN
		Sinergias entre la valorización de residuos y la remediación de suelos	ES
4	Practice Abstract 11	Sustainable soil management practices for peri-urban agricultural lands	EN
		Održive prakse gospodarenja tlom na periurbanim poljoprivrednim zemljištima	HR
	Practice Abstract 12	Enhancing forest and grassland soil health in peri-urban areas	EN
		Poboljšanje zdravlja šumskih i travnjačkih tala u periurbanim područjima	HR
	Practice Abstract 13	Smart urban planning can enhance carbon storage and mitigate flood effect	EN
		Urbano planiranje može poboljšati pohranu ugljika i ublažiti učinak poplava	HR
5	Practice Abstract 14	Baltupiai urban gardens soil quality recovery	EN
		Baltupių miesto sodų dirvožemio kokybės atkūrimas	LT
	Practice Abstract 15	Management of urban lawns	EN
		Miesto vejų tvarkymas	LT
	Practice Abstract 16	Vegetation management impact on thermal properties in urban park on climate regulation	EN
		Vegetation management impact on thermal properties in urban park on climate regulation	LT

Table 1c. List of Practice Abstracts 17-22 (batch 1)

LH/LL	Practice Abstract	Title	Language
6	Practice Abstract 17	Forest fertilization sustainability	EN
		Ilgstspējīga mežaudžu mēslošana	LV
	Practice Abstract 18	Mining site recultivation	EN
		Derīgo izrakteņu ieguves vietu rekultivācija	LV
	Practice Abstract 19	Forest regeneration practices- importance of planting site	EN
		Meža atjaunošanas - stādīšanas vietas nozīme	LV
7	Practice Abstract 20	Diverse cover crop mixes	EN
		Diverse groenbemester mengsels	NL
	Practice Abstract 21	Soil building crop rotation	EN
		Bodemopbouwende vruchtwisseling	NL
	Practice Abstract 22	Johnson-Su composting	EN
		Johnson-Su composteren	NL

Table 1d. List of Practice Abstracts 23-28 (batch 1)

LH/LL	Practice Abstract	Title	Language
LL-1	Practice Abstract 23	Conservation agriculture for sustainability cereal systems in the Mediterranean	EN
		Agricoltura conservativa per la sostenibilità dei sistemi cerealicoli nel Mediterraneo	IT
	Practice Abstract 24	Conservation tillages and soil carbon	EN
		Lavorazioni conservative e carbonio nel suolo	IT
	Practice Abstract 25	Conservation Tillage and Soil Water Content	EN
		Lavorazioni conservative e contenuto d'acqua nel suolo	IT
LL-2	Practice Abstract 26	Enhancing soil resilience and carbon sequestration through reduced tillage: a practical approach for farmers	EN
		Verbesserung der Widerstandsfähigkeit des Bodens und der Kohlenstoffbindung durch reduzierte Bodenbearbeitung: ein praktischer Ansatz für Landwirte	DE
	Practice Abstract 27	Farm Soil Health Practice Adoption Benchmarking: Enabling Individual Performance Comparison	EN
		Benchmarking für die Einführung von Bodengesundheitspraktiken in landwirtschaftlichen Betrieben: Ermöglichung eines individuellen Leistungsvergleichs	DE
	Practice Abstract 28	Undersowing	EN
		Untersaaten	DE

Annex I: Collection of Practice Abstract Factsheets

Lighthouse 1

Practice Abstract #01

Enhancing soil health through rotational grazing in mediterranean forestry

Authors: Elena de Julián¹, María Catalán²

Objective

In Mediterranean forestry, soil health is frequently compromised due to poor vegetative growth, lack of humidity, and suboptimal temperature conditions for microbiological activity. Continuous soil degradation and desertification present additional challenges. This abstract addresses how rotational grazing can mitigate these issues by promoting vegetative recovery and improving soil conditions.

Result

Implementing rotational grazing in Mediterranean forests has proven to reduce soil degradation by preventing overgrazing and erosion. The reintroduction of controlled grazing cycles allows for periods of plant regeneration, contributing to better soil structure, increased organic matter, and enhanced microbiological activity. These improvements have also led to higher soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks, which play a critical role in mitigating climate change.

Recommendations

Forest managers and landowners can adopt rotational grazing systems to improve soil health and prevent land degradation. By regulating grazing intensity and allowing recovery periods for vegetation, soil structure can be maintained and enriched, while SOC levels are conserved. For optimal results, rotational grazing should be tailored to local climate conditions, vegetation types, and livestock density.

Figure 01: Grazing management through the "Carbon Pump" in LH1

¹ Fundación Global Nature (FGN). ² Actyva Sociedad Cooperativa.

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Practice Abstract #01

Mejora de la calidad del suelo mediante el pastoreo rotacional en bosques mediterráneos

Autores: Elena de Julián¹, María Catalán²

Objetivo

En el bosque Mediterráneo, la salud del suelo se ve frecuentemente comprometida debido al escaso crecimiento vegetativo, la falta de humedad y condiciones de temperatura poco favorables para la actividad microbiológica. La continua degradación del suelo y la desertificación suponen un reto para esta actividad. Este documento muestra cómo el pastoreo rotacional puede mitigar estos problemas mejorando la calidad de estos suelos.

Recomendaciones

Los silvicultores y ganaderos pueden adoptar sistemas de pastoreo rotacional para mejorar la salud del suelo y evitar su degradación. El sistema de rotación de ganado permite periodos de recuperación para la vegetación, manteniendo y enriqueciendo la estructura del suelo mientras se conservan los niveles de COS. Los mejores resultados se obtiene adaptando el pastoreo rotacional a las condiciones climáticas locales, tipos de vegetación y densidad del ganado.

Resultado

El pastoreo rotacional en la silvicultura Mediterránea ha demostrado reducir la degradación del suelo evitando el sobrepastoreo y la erosión. La introducción de ciclos de pastoreo controlados permite la regeneración vegetal, contribuyendo a mejorar la estructura del suelo, incrementando la materia orgánica del mismo y potenciando la actividad microbiológica. Estas medidas también han permitido aumentar las reservas de carbono orgánico del suelo (COS) contribuyendo de forma muy positiva a la mitigación del cambio climático.

Figura 01: Gestión del pastoreo mediante la «bomba de carbono» en LH1

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Practice Abstract #02

Carbon pump: how cattle help to increase soil carbon storage

Authors: Elena de Julián¹, María Catalán²

Objective

The main objective is to reduce land degradation related to desertification and to conserve and increase soil organic carbon reserves. Based on the premise that herbivores play a key role in maintaining adequate parameters for soil health, controlled grazing is used to activate the nutrient decomposition circuit necessary for healthy soil.

Result

Carbon storage increased fertility and quality of soil through herbivores rotational grazing and its "carbon pump". The "carbon pump" emulates a pumping system to increase the availability of carbon and nutrients in the edaphic cycle dynamics. Herbivores eat the grass which alter plant growth and promotes roots decomposition that transform the residues into organic carbon and give some nutrients off. This availability reactivates a cycle of growth. The grazing management is essential to favour the balance of the system.

UNPLANNED grazing

Constant access to all pasture, leading to overgrazing.

ROTATIONAL grazing

Access to plots adapted to changing conditions.

Figure 01: Differences between unplanned and rotational grazing.

¹ Fundación Global Nature (FGN). ² Actyva Sociedad Cooperativa.

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Recommendations

To maximise environmental and production benefits, we should promote short and intense grazing pulses.

1. It is advisable to divide the plots to carry out rotational grazing and rationing.
2. In addition, high animal density and grazing times of no more than 3 days-followed by extended rest times-allow plant and soil recovery.
3. Time recovery is key and vary according to climatic conditions and the particular context of each farm.

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Practice Abstract #02

Bomba de carbono: aumento del almacenamiento de carbono en el suelo gracias al ganado

Autores: Elena de Julián¹, María Catalán²

Objetivo

El principal objetivo de la bomba de carbono es reducir la degradación del suelo relacionada con la desertificación, conservando e incrementando las reservas de carbono orgánico del suelo. Los herbívoros desempeñan un papel fundamental en el mantenimiento de los parámetros adecuados para la salud del suelo. Gracias al pastoreo controlado se activa el circuito de descomposición de nutrientes necesarios para mejorar la salud del suelo.

Resultado

El almacenamiento de carbono aumenta la fertilidad y la calidad del suelo. Por medio del pastoreo rotacional se pone en funcionamiento la "bomba de carbono". Este sistema emula un sistema de bombeo que incrementa la disponibilidad de carbono y nutrientes en la dinámica del ciclo edáfico. Los herbívoros se comen la vegetación, lo que altera el crecimiento de las plantas y favorece la descomposición de las raíces, transformando los residuos en carbono orgánico y liberando nutrientes. De esta forma se reactiva el ciclo de crecimiento. La gestión del pastoreo es esencial para favorecer el equilibrio del sistema.

PASTOREO no planificado

Acceso constante a todo el pasto, lo que lleva al sobrepastoreo.

PASTOREO rotacional

Acceso a parcelas adaptadas a condiciones cambiantes.

Figura 01: Diferencias entre pastoreo no planificado y pastoreo rotacional.

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Recomendaciones

Para maximizar los beneficios medioambientales y la producción es importante realizar pulsos cortos de pastoreo y descansos acordes:

1. Es necesario dividir el terreno en potreros
2. Una alta densidad de ganado y tiempos de pastoreo no superiores a tres días permiten la recuperación de la vegetación y el suelo
3. Es tiempo de recuperación es un parámetro vital, y dependerá de las condiciones climáticas y del contexto particular de cada explotación.

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Practice Abstract #03

A management practice that improves soil and pasture productivity through controlled livestock impact

Authors: Elena de Julián¹, María Catalán²

Objective

Penning is an ancient practice in which livestock are confined to mobile pens during the night or siesta in an itinerant manner, with the goal of fertilizing the soil and potentially improving pastures, controlling shrubs, and protecting animals from predators.

Result

Finca El Baldío, located in Talaván, Cáceres, is a dehesa, a Mediterranean agro-silvopastoral system with perennial herbs, oaks, and livestock use, where sheep penning has been combined with rotational grazing since 2022. The results obtained for 2 indicators (Soil Fauna Diversity Index and % Bare Soil) across 3 zones with different management practices within the same farm are shown in the table below.

	Shannon Index 2019	Shannon Index 2024	% Bare soil 2019	% Bare soil 2024
Penning zone	2,4	2,6	10,1	1,5
Conventional management zone	2,2	2,5	11,0	17,9

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Recommendations

- The pens are made with metal gates or electric mesh. Metal gates are more durable and secure but are more difficult to move. Electric mesh is quicker to install and reduces costs but may suffer voltage drops if the ground is dry or the shrubbery is too tall.
- The size of the pen depends on the number of animals. A surface area of 1-2m² per sheep is typically calculated.
- The pen will be moved every 3-4 days on average to adjacent areas. It is essential to avoid leaving livestock on waterlogged land.
- It is recommended to combine this practice with appropriate grazing management, ensuring the rest period of the penned area until plant recovery occurs.

Impact on penning areas: The photo on the left shows the area before entry, and the photo on the right shows it after the sheep spent the night.

Diagram of the penning process: The flock is moved to an adjacent plot after 2 or 3 nights of overnight stay.

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Practice Abstract #03

Práctica de manejo que mejora el suelo y la productividad de los pastos gracias al impacto controlado del ganado

Autores: Elena de Julián¹, María Catalán²

Objetivo

El redileo es una práctica ancestral en la que, de manera itinerante, se confina a los animales en corrales móviles durante la pernocta o el sesteo con el objetivo de fertilizar los suelos y, potencialmente, mejorar los pastos, controlar los matorrales y proteger a los animales de depredadores.

Resultado

La finca El Baldío en Talaván, Cáceres, es una dehesa, sistema agrosilvopastoral mediterráneo con herbáceas perennes, quercíneas y de uso ganadero, en la que se implementa redileo de ovejas, combinado con pastoreo rotacional desde 2022. Los resultados obtenidos para 2 indicadores (Índice de diversidad de fauna edáfica y % de suelo desnudo) en 3 zonas con manejos diferentes dentro de la misma finca, se muestran en la siguiente tabla.

	Índice Shannon 2019	Índice Shannon 2024	% Suelo desnudo 2019	% Suelo desnudo 2024
Zona de redileo	2,4	2,6	10,1	1,5
Zona de manejo convencional	2,2	2,5	11,0	17,9

Es llamativa la disminución de suelo desnudo en la zona de redileo, y el aumento en la zona de manejo convencional a lo largo de 5 años.

En las fotografías se muestra el impacto de una noche de redileo en el control del matorral, por pisoteo y depredación.

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Recomendaciones

- Los corrales o rediles se realizan con cancelas metálicas o malla eléctrica. Las cancelas metálicas son más resistentes y seguras, pero más difíciles de trasladar. La malla eléctrica es más rápida de instalar y permite abaratar costes, pero pueden ocurrir caídas de tensión si el suelo está seco o el matorral es muy elevado.
- La superficie del redil dependerá del número de animales. Se suele calcular una superficie de 1-2m² por oveja.
- El corral se moverá cada 3-4 días de media a zonas adyacentes. Se evitará en cualquier caso que el ganado permanezca sobre terreno encharcado.
- Se recomienda compaginar la práctica con manejos adecuados del pastoreo, asegurando el descanso de la parcela redileada hasta la recuperación de las plantas.

Impacto en las áreas de redileo: La foto de la izquierda muestra el área antes de entrar, y la de la derecha después de que las ovejas pasaron la noche.

Esquema del proceso de redileo: el rebaño se muda a una parcela adyacente tras 2 o 3 noches de pernocta.

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Lighthouse 2

Practice Abstract #04

Enhancing soil health through the creation of artificial soils (Technosols) in tailings ponds.

Authors: Raúl Zornoza, Silvia Martínez Martínez, José A. Acosta, Virginia Sánchez Navarro, María Dolores Gómez López, Ángel Faz ¹

Objective

The environmental impact caused by the waste produced by mining and metallurgical activities has resulted in marked negative effects on soil, water resources (surface, groundwater and marine water), landscape, atmosphere and biota. The risk of erosion by water and wind is the most important environmental issue due to its implications. The main objective of this intervention is the creation of artificial soils (Technosols) associated to aided phytostabilization techniques (introduction of heavy metal-tolerant plants) to enhance soil health in tailings ponds and allow the development of a native vegetation cover. The reclamation so consisted of the creation of Technosols by the use of organic (slurry and manure) and inorganic (tailings and marble waste) materials. Main species introduced were *Piptaterum miliaceum*, *Salvia rosmarinus*, *Dittrichia viscosa*, or *Hyparrhenia hirta*.

Result

The adoption of Technosols and phytostabilisation technique led to an increase in soil health, with the development of the planted vegetation, but also the introduction of native species from the surroundings, with a vegetation cover of grasses and shrubs of around 50%, compared to the complete absence of vegetation before reclamation. This was due to increases in pH from 4 to 7 owing to the Technosols, with decreases in soil electrical conductivity (salinity) from 2.5 dS/m to 1.5 dS/m. Soil organic carbon increased from 0.93 g/kg to 7.93 g/kg. Total nitrogen increased from 0.00 g/kg to 0.28 g/kg, available phosphorus from 0.00 mg/kg to 11.50 mg/kg, or exchangeable potassium from 4 cmol/kg to 34 cmol/kg. Soil structure also improved with higher diameter of stable aggregates and microbial biomass increased from 2 ng/kg to 14 ng/kg. Thus, all soil health indicators were improved with the reclamation strategy, leading to the growth of a native vegetation cover.

¹ Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena.

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Recommendations

The use of Technosols by the mixture of different materials as marble waste or pig slurry and manure ensures that associated to the plantation of heavy metal resistant vegetation, it becomes an effective strategy to enhance soil health and promote the development of native vegetation in abandoned metallic tailings.

Recovered mining area with a Technosol and native shrub vegetation.

Tailings ponds in an abandoned mining site.

Soil sampling at an unreclaimed abandoned mine site.

Soil sampling in a reclaimed mining area with a Technosol and native shrub vegetation.

¹ Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena.

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Practice Abstract #04

Mejora de la salud del suelo mediante la creación de suelos artificiales (Tecnosoles) en depósitos de relaves mineros.

Autores: Raúl Zornoza, Silvia Martínez Martínez, José A. Acosta, Virginia Sánchez Navarro, María Dolores Gómez López, Ángel Faz ¹

Objetivo

El impacto ambiental causado por los residuos producidos por actividades mineras y metalúrgicas ha resultado en efectos negativos significativos en el suelo, los recursos hídricos (agua superficial, subterránea y marina), el paisaje, la atmósfera y la biota. El riesgo de erosión por agua y viento es el problema ambiental más importante debido a sus implicaciones. El objetivo principal de esta intervención es la creación de suelos artificiales (Tecnosoles) asociados a técnicas de fitostabilización asistida (introducción de plantas tolerantes a metales pesados) para mejorar la salud del suelo en depósitos de relaves mineros, y permitir el desarrollo de una cubierta vegetal nativa. La recuperación consistió en la creación de Tecnosoles mediante el uso de materiales orgánicos (purines y estiércol) e inorgánicos (relaves y residuos de mármol). Las principales especies introducidas fueron *Piptaterum miliaceum*, *Salvia rosmarinus*, *Dittrichia viscosa* e *Hyparrhenia hirta*.

Resultado

El uso de Tecnosoles y la técnica de fitoestabilización condujo a un aumento en la salud del suelo, con el desarrollo de la vegetación introducida por plantación y también la colonización espontánea de especies nativas de los alrededores, logrando una cobertura vegetal de gramíneas y arbustos de alrededor del 50%, en comparación con la ausencia total de vegetación antes de la recuperación. Esto se debió a aumentos en el pH de 4 a 7 gracias a los Tecnosoles, con disminuciones en la conductividad eléctrica del suelo (salinidad) de 2,5 dS/m a 1,5 dS/m. El carbono orgánico del suelo aumentó de 0,93 g/kg a 7,93 g/kg. El nitrógeno total aumentó de 0,00 g/kg a 0,28 g/kg, el fósforo disponible de 0,00 mg/kg a 11,50 mg/kg, y el potasio intercambiable de 4 cmol/kg a 34 cmol/kg. La estructura del suelo también mejoró con un mayor diámetro de agregados estables, y la biomasa microbiana aumentó de 2 ng/kg a 14 ng/kg. Así, todos los indicadores de salud del suelo mejoraron con la estrategia de recuperación, lo que permitió el crecimiento de una cubierta vegetal nativa.

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Recomendaciones

El uso de Tecnosoles mediante la mezcla de diferentes materiales, como residuos de mármol o purines y estiércol, asociado a la plantación de vegetación resistente a metales pesados, es una estrategia eficaz para mejorar la salud del suelo y promover el desarrollo de vegetación nativa en relaves metálicos abandonados.

Zona minera recuperada con un Tecnosol y vegetación arbustiva autóctona.

Balsas de residuos en una zona minera abandonada

Muestreo del suelo en un emplazamiento minero abandonado sin recuperación.

Muestreo de suelo en zona minera recuperada con un Tecnosol y vegetación arbustiva autóctona.

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Practice Abstract #05

Reclamation of tailings pond using Technosols and phytostabilization leads to pollution reduction.

Authors: Raúl Zornoza, Silvia Martínez Martínez, José A. Acosta, Virginia Sánchez-Navarro, Ángel Faz ¹

Objective

Pollution dispersion from the mining area by water and wind erosion also reaches cities, recreative areas and even croplands. The chronic exposure to airborne pollutants from tailings can lead to health risks for the surrounding populations. Considering the limiting conditions of the soils it was essential to realize a sustainable alternative for the reclamation of mining sites using the strategy of aided phytostabilization and Technosols. Thus, the main objective of this intervention is the creation of artificial soils (Technosols) associated to aided phytostabilization techniques (introduction of heavy metal-tolerant plants) to reduce the availability of metal pollutants in tailings ponds to avoid their dispersion through erosion. The reclamation so consisted of the creation of Technosols by the use of organic (slurry and manure) and inorganic (tailings and marble waste) materials. Main species introduced were *Piptaterum miliaceum*, *Salvia rosmarinus*, *Dittrichia viscosa*, or *Hyparrhenia hirta*.

Result

The use of Technosols associated to aided phytostabilisation led to a decreased of 95-99% of the availability of metals (Pb, Cu, Zn, Cd) and metalloids (As) in the soil, reducing toxicity for plant development and risks for transportation by leaching or erosion. This has been due to the increase in pH by the creation of the Technosol with the addition of calcium carbonate to buffer soil pH (values around 7) and the presence of plant species able to immobilise metals and metalloids in their rhizosphere and roots such as *Piptaterum miliaceum* or *Hyparrhenia hirta*.

Recommendations

Using Technosols created with marble waste (calcium carbonate), pig slurry/manure and tailings, and its combination with aided phytostabilisation is an efficient strategy to reclaim tailings ponds in order to decrease soil pollution by heavy metals and metalloids.

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Tailing ponds in an abandoned mine area.

Tailing ponds in an abandoned mine area.

Soil sampling in reclaimed mine area with a Technosol and native shrub vegetation.

Reclaimed mining area with a Technosol and native shrub vegetation (mining building to access the mine at the background: cultural element)

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Practice Abstract #05

La rehabilitación de depósitos de relaves mineros mediante el uso de Tecnosuelos y fitoestabilización conduce a la reducción de la contaminación.

Autores: Raúl Zornoza, Silvia Martínez Martínez, José A. Acosta, Virginia Sánchez-Navarro, Ángel Faz ¹

Objetivo

La dispersión de la contaminación desde las áreas mineras por erosión hídrica y eólica también alcanza ciudades, áreas recreativas e incluso tierras de cultivo. La exposición crónica a contaminantes en suspensión procedentes de los relaves puede generar riesgos para la salud de las poblaciones circundantes. Considerando las condiciones limitantes de los suelos, fue esencial implementar una alternativa sostenible para la recuperación de sitios mineros mediante la estrategia de fitoestabilización asistida y el uso de Tecnosoles. Así, el objetivo principal de esta intervención es la creación de suelos artificiales (Tecnosoles) asociados a técnicas de fitoestabilización asistida (introducción de plantas tolerantes a metales pesados) para reducir la disponibilidad de contaminantes metálicos en los estanques de relaves y evitar su dispersión por erosión. La recuperación consistió en la creación de Tecnosoles mediante el uso de materiales orgánicos (purines y estiércol) e inorgánicos (relaves y residuos de mármol). Las principales especies introducidas fueron *Piptaterum miliaceum*, *Salvia rosmarinus*, *Dittrichia viscosa* e *Hyparrhenia hirta*.

Resultado

El uso de Tecnosoles asociado a la fitoestabilización asistida condujo a una disminución del 95-99% de la disponibilidad de metales (Pb, Cu, Zn, Cd) y metaloides (As) en el suelo, reduciendo la toxicidad para el desarrollo de las plantas y los riesgos de transporte por lixiviación o erosión. Esto se debe al aumento del pH mediante la creación del Tecnosol con la adición de carbonato de calcio para amortiguar el pH del suelo (valores alrededor de 7) y la presencia de especies vegetales capaces de inmovilizar metales y metaloides en su rizosfera y raíces, como *Piptaterum miliaceum* o *Hyparrhenia hirta*.

Recomendaciones

El uso de Tecnosoles creados con residuos de mármol (carbonato de calcio), purines/estiércol y relaves, combinado junto con la fitoestabilización asistida, es una estrategia eficiente para la recuperación de depósitos de relaves con el fin de reducir la contaminación del suelo por metales pesados y metaloides.

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Balsas de residuos en una zona minera abandonada.

Balsas de residuos en una zona minera abandonada.

Muestreo de suelos en zona minera recuperada con un Tecnosol y vegetación arbustiva autóctona.

Zona minera recuperada con un Tecnosol y vegetación arbustiva autóctona (edificio minero de acceso a la mina al fondo: elemento cultural).

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Practice Abstract #06

Non-Market Value of ecosystem services associated with rehabilitated tailing ponds using tecnosols and phytostabilization.

Authors: Jorge Luis Sánchez, Raúl Zornoza, José Antonio Albaladejo, Francisco Alcón ¹

Objective

The environmental impact caused by the waste produced by mining and metallurgical activities has resulted in marked negative effects on soil, water resources, landscapes, the atmosphere, and biota. To address this issue, an intervention was carried out involving the creation of artificial soils (Tecnosols) by the use of organic (slurry and manure) and inorganic (tailings and marble waste) materials. The main species introduced were *Piptatherum miliaceum*, *Salvia rosmarinus*, *Dittrichia viscosa*, and *Hyparrhenia hirta*. The benefits associated with this intervention extend beyond soil health improvement, as they include the enhancement of ecosystem services such as CO₂ sequestration, which contributes to climate change mitigation; water absorption, which improves water regulation and reduces erosion risks; and increased recreational opportunities through the creation of a rehabilitated landscape that can be enjoyed by people. The objective of this work is to assign an economic value to these intangible services, considering their non-market nature, in order to reflect their importance to society and the environment.

Result

The use of Tecnosols and the phytostabilization technique resulted in an increase in soil carbon sequestration of 5.5 tons of CO₂ per hectare per year, which, in monetary terms, equates to €79.31 annually for the total area intervened (1.4 hectares). Additionally, water absorption capacity was increased by 40 m³ per hectare per year, valued at €4.69 annually; and an increase of 1,910 annual visitors was recorded, estimated generate an economic value of €12,728 per year. Overall, the economic value generated by the enhancement in ecosystem service provision amounts to €12,812 annually. In a scenario with unlimited lifespan, considering a low-risk interest rate of 2.24% (10-year German bond) and a stable inflation rate of 2% (ECB monetary policy target), this annual value, discounted to present terms, amounts to €299,010.54.

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Recommendations

The use of Technosols and phytostabilization to rehabilitate mine tailings improves soil health and generates additional benefits, such as CO₂ sequestration, water absorption, and the creation of a recreational landscape. These non-market ecosystem services have an economic value that can be quantified, which is essential for highlighting their social and environmental significance.

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Practice Abstract #06

Valor de no mercado de los servicios ecosistémicos asociados a depósitos de relaves mineros rehabilitados mediante el uso de Tecnosuelos y fitoestabilización.

Autores: Jorge Luis Sánchez, Raúl Zornoza, José Antonio Albaladejo, Francisco Alcón ¹

Objetivo

El impacto ambiental causado por los residuos producidos por actividades mineras y metalúrgicas ha generado efectos negativos significativos en el suelo, los recursos hídricos, el paisaje, la atmósfera y la biota. Para abordar este problema se realizó una intervención que consistió en la creación de Tecnosuelos mediante el uso de materiales orgánicos (purines y estiércol) e inorgánicos (relaves y residuos de mármol). Las principales especies introducidas fueron *Piptaterum miliaceum*, *Salvia rosmarinus*, *Dittrichia viscosa* e *Hyparrhenia hirta*. Los beneficios asociados a esta intervención van más allá de la mejora de la salud del suelo ya que suponen la mejora en servicios ecosistémicos como el secuestro de CO₂ que contribuye a mitigar el cambio climático; la absorción de agua, que mejora la regulación hídrica y reduce riesgos de erosión; y el aumento de oportunidades recreativas, al ofrecer un paisaje rehabilitado que puede ser disfrutado por las personas. El objetivo de este trabajo es asignar un valor económico a estos servicios intangibles, considerando su naturaleza de no mercado que permite reflejar su importancia para la sociedad y el medio ambiente.

Resultado

El uso de Tecnosuelos y la técnica de fitoestabilización resultó en un aumento del secuestro de carbono en el suelo de 5,5 toneladas CO₂ por hectárea al año, lo que, en términos monetarios, equivale a 79,31€ anuales para la superficie total intervenida (1,4 hectáreas). Además, se incrementó la capacidad de absorción de agua en 40m³ por hectárea al año, valorado en 4,69€ anuales; y se registró un aumento de 1910 visitantes anuales, lo que se estima que tiene un valor económico de 12.728€ al año. En conjunto, el valor económico generado por la mejora en la provisión de servicios ecosistémicos asciende a 12,812€ al año. En un escenario de vida útil ilimitada, considerando un tipo de interés de bajo riesgo del 2,24% (bono alemán a 10 años) y una tasa de inflación estable del 2% (objetivo de la política monetaria del BCE), este valor anual actualizado al presente equivale a 299.010,54€.

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Recomendaciones

El uso de Tecnosoles y fitostabilización para rehabilitar depósitos de relaves mineros mejora la salud del suelo y genera beneficios adicionales, como el secuestro de CO₂, la absorción de agua y la creación de un paisaje recreativo. Estos servicios ecosistémicos de no mercado poseen un valor económico que puede ser cuantificado, lo cual es crucial para reflejar su importancia social y ambiental.

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Practice Abstract #07

Reclamation of tailings pond using Technosols and phytostabilization increases soil microbial diversity and abundance.

Authors: Eva Lloret, Raúl Zornoza, Silvia Martínez-Martínez, José A. Acosta, Virginia Sánchez-Navarro, Ángel Faz¹

Objective

Mine tailings and soils with high content of metals hinders the development of soil organisms, with low abundance and diversity. This leads to reduced soil functionality and so, delivery of ecosystem services. Considering the limiting conditions of these soils it was essential to realize a sustainable alternative for the reclamation of mining sites using the strategy of aided phytostabilization and Technosols. Thus, the main objective of this intervention is the creation of artificial soils (Technosols) associated to aided phytostabilization techniques (introduction of heavy metal-tolerant plants) to increase soil health and enhance soil bacterial and fungal abundance and diversity. The reclamation so consisted of the creation of Technosols by the use of organic (slurry and manure) and inorganic (tailings and marble waste) materials. Main species introduced were *Piptatherum miliaceum*, *Salvia rosmarinus*, *Dittrichia viscosa*, or *Hyparrhenia hirta*.

Result

Unreclaimed tailings showed such a low microbial biomass, that was impossible to extract DNA at the required quantities to characterize the composition of microbial communities. However, the use of Technosols associated to aided phytostabilisation led to an increase in microbial biomass, so DNA could be extracted, and microbial community characterised. The bacterial Shannon Index was 9.81 and fungal Shannon Index was 4.57. Dominant bacterial genera were *Sphingomonas*, *Dongia*, *Vicinamibacteraceae* and *Streptomyces*. Dominant fungal genera *Thelephora*, *Penicillium*, *Aspergillus*, *Thichoderma*, *Hygrocybe*, *Pisolithus* and *Talaromyces*. Total microbial biomass, expressed as total phospholipid fatty acids extracted from cell membranes, was 2.75 nmol/g in the unreclaimed tailing soil, and increased to 13.00 nmol/g in the Technosol. Thus, microbial biomass and bacterial and fungal diversity increased with the reclamation strategy.

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Recommendations

Using Technosols created with marble waste (calcium carbonate), pig slurry/manure and tailings, and its combination with aided phytostabilisation is an efficient strategy to reclaim tailings ponds in order to increase soil microbial biomass and diversity, vital to reestablish soil functionality.

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Practice Abstract #07

La rehabilitación de depósitos de relaves mineros mediante el uso de Tecnosuelos y fitoestabilización incrementa la abundancia y diversidad de microorganismos del suelo.

Autores: Eva Lloret, Raúl Zornoza, Silvia Martínez-Martínez, José A. Acosta, Virginia Sánchez-Navarro, Ángel Faz¹

Objetivo

Los relaves y suelos mineros con alto contenido en metales dificulta el desarrollo de organismos en el suelo, con baja abundancia y diversidad. Esto conduce a una reducción de la funcionalidad edáfica y por tanto, de los servicios ecosistémicos asociados. Considerando las condiciones limitantes de estos suelos, fue esencial implementar una alternativa sostenible para la recuperación de sitios mineros mediante la estrategia de fitostabilización asistida y el uso de Tecnosoles. Así, el objetivo principal de esta intervención es la creación de suelos artificiales (Tecnosoles) asociados a técnicas de fitostabilización asistida (introducción de plantas tolerantes a metales pesados) para incrementar la salud del suelo y la abundancia y diversidad de las comunidades bacterianas y fúngicas del suelo. La recuperación consistió en la creación de Tecnosoles mediante el uso de materiales orgánicos (purines y estiércol) e inorgánicos (relaves y residuos de mármol). Las principales especies introducidas fueron *Piptaterum miliaceum*, *Salvia rosmarinus*, *Dittrichia viscosa* e *Hypparrhenia hirta*.

Resultado

Los suelos mineros sin rehabilitar mostraron una biomasa microbiana tan baja que fue imposible extraer ADN en las cantidades necesarias para caracterizar la composición de las comunidades microbianas. Sin embargo, el uso de Tecnosoles asociados a la fitoestabilización asistida condujo a un aumento en la biomasa microbiana, lo que permitió extraer ADN y caracterizar la comunidad microbiana. El índice de diversidad de Shannon para bacterias fue de 9,81 y para hongos de 4,57. Los géneros bacterianos dominantes fueron *Sphingomonas*, *Dongia*, *Vicinamibacteraceae* y *Streptomyces*. Los géneros fúngicos dominantes fueron *Thelephora*, *Penicillium*, *Aspergillus*, *Trichoderma*, *Hygrocybe*, *Pisolithus* y *Talaromyces*. La biomasa microbiana total, expresada como ácidos grasos fosfolípidicos totales extraídos de las membranas celulares, fue de 2.75 nmol/g en los suelos mineros no recuperados, y aumentó a 13.00 nmol/g en el Tecnosol. Por lo tanto, la biomasa microbiana y la diversidad bacteriana y fúngica aumentaron con la estrategia de recuperación.

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Recomendaciones

El uso de Tecnosoles creados con residuos de mármol (carbonato de calcio), purines/estiércol y relaves, combinado junto con la fitostabilización asistida, es una estrategia eficiente para la recuperación de depósitos de relaves con el fin de incrementar la biomasa y diversidad microbiana, necesario para restablecer las funciones del suelo.

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Lighthouse 3

Practice Abstract #08

Restoration of degraded mining soils with Technosols: the mine of Touro

Author: Javier de Rivera Outomuro¹

Objective

The Touro mine, exploited for copper extraction between 1974 and 1988, experienced extreme soil degradation, leaving behind hyperacidic soils with no vegetation. The rapid oxidation of sulfides and contamination of nearby rivers were the main environmental issues. This abstract addresses the use of technosols for soil rehabilitation and the reactivation of biological processes in the affected area.

Recommendations

The application of technosols in degraded mining areas can be an effective solution to restore soil fertility and promote the growth of native flora and fauna. To achieve optimal results, it is essential to select suitable materials that reduce sulfide oxidation and provide the necessary nutrients to reactivate soil biota. This technique is replicable in other mines with similar conditions and contributes to long-term ecological sustainability.

Result

Technosols, made from mixtures of inorganic and organic waste (such as mussel shells and biomass ash), successfully neutralized soil acidity and restored biological activity. Over 23 years, the treated areas have developed diverse vegetation (pines, eucalyptus, and native species) and local fauna such as rabbits, foxes, and birds of prey. Additionally, these soils demonstrated a high capacity for carbon retention (with >12% organic carbon in surface horizons), contributing to climate change mitigation.

Image 1: Close-up view of the technosoil

Image 2: General view of the Touro mine in the process of regeneration.

¹ Centro de Valorización Ambiental del Norte (CVAN).

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Practice Abstract #08

Restauración de suelos degradados con Tecnosoles: La mina de Touro

Autor: Javier de Rivera Outomuro¹

Objetivo

La mina de Touro, explotada para la extracción de cobre entre 1974 y 1988, sufrió una degradación extrema del suelo, que dejó suelos hiperácidos y sin vegetación. La rápida oxidación de los sulfuros y la contaminación de los ríos cercanos fueron los principales problemas ambientales. En este resumen se aborda el uso de tecnosoles para la rehabilitación de suelos y la reactivación de procesos biológicos en la zona afectada.

Recomendaciones

La aplicación de tecnosoles en áreas mineras degradadas puede ser una solución eficaz para restaurar la fertilidad del suelo y promover el crecimiento de la flora y fauna nativas. Para lograr resultados óptimos, es fundamental seleccionar materiales adecuados que reduzcan la oxidación de sulfuros y aporten los nutrientes necesarios para reactivar la biota del suelo. Esta técnica es replicable en otras minas con condiciones similares y contribuye a la sostenibilidad ecológica a largo plazo.

Resultado

Los tecnosoles, elaborados a partir de la mezcla de desechos inorgánicos y orgánicos (como conchas de mejillones y cenizas de biomasa), neutralizaron con éxito la acidez del suelo y restauraron la actividad biológica en una antigua mina de cobre. A lo largo de 23 años, las áreas tratadas han desarrollado una vegetación diversa (pinos, eucaliptos y especies nativas) y fauna local como conejos, zorros y aves rapaces. Además, estos suelos demostraron una alta capacidad de retención de carbono (con >12% de carbono orgánico en horizontes superficiales), lo que contribuye a la mitigación del cambio climático.

Imagen 1: Primer plano del tecnosol

Imagen 2: Vista de la Mina de Touro en proceso de regeneración

¹ Centro de Valorización Ambiental del Norte (CVAN).

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Practice Abstract #09

Reactive wetlands for the treatment of hyperacidic waters

Author: Javier de Rivera Outomuro¹

Objective

Acid mine drainage from the Touro mine, caused by the oxidation of sulfides, resulted in severe water contamination, with extremely low pH and high levels of sulfates and heavy metals. This abstract discusses the construction of an artificial reactive wetland to improve water quality and restore the aquatic ecosystem.

Result

Since the creation of the reactive wetland in 2002, the hyperacidic waters from the mine have been treated using specialized technosols, successfully neutralizing pH (values close to 7) and significantly reducing sulfate and aluminum levels. Since 2008, the system was self-sustaining, allowing the reappearance of aquatic insects, amphibians, and birds. Furthermore, the aquatic ecosystem stabilized, with the food chain completed by the return of predators such as birds of prey.

Recommendations

Reactive wetlands with technosols are an effective solution for treating hyperacidic waters in mining areas, restoring not only water quality but also biodiversity. This technique can be applied in other mining sites affected by acid drainage. Regular monitoring of Eh-pH conditions and adjustments in the composition of technosols are recommended to maximize sulfate and heavy metal retention, ensuring the sustainability of the recovered aquatic ecosystem.

Image 01: Touro Mine, 2010.

Image 02: Touro Mine, 2005.

Image 03: Touro Mine, 2002..

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Practice Abstract #09

Humedales reactivos para el tratamiento de aguas hiperácidas

Autor: Javier de Rivera Outomuro¹

Objetivo

El drenaje ácido de la mina de Touro, causado por la oxidación de sulfuros, provocó una grave contaminación del agua, con un pH extremadamente bajo y altos niveles de sulfatos y metales pesados. En este resumen se analiza la construcción de un humedal reactivo artificial para mejorar la calidad del agua y restaurar el ecosistema acuático.

Resultado

Desde la creación del humedal reactivo en 2002, las aguas hiperácidas de la mina han sido tratadas con tecnosoles especializados, logrando neutralizar el pH (valores cercanos a 7) y reducir significativamente los niveles de sulfato y aluminio. En 2008, el sistema ya era autosostenible, lo que permitió la reaparición de insectos acuáticos, anfibios y aves. Además, el ecosistema acuático se estabilizó, completándose la cadena alimentaria con el regreso de depredadores como las aves rapaces.

Recomendaciones

Los humedales reactivos con tecnosoles son una solución eficaz para el tratamiento de aguas hiperácidas en zonas mineras, restaurando no sólo la calidad del agua sino también la biodiversidad. Esta técnica puede aplicarse en otras áreas mineras afectados por drenaje ácido. Se recomienda el monitoreo regular de las condiciones de Eh-pH y los ajustes en la composición de los tecnosoles para maximizar la retención de sulfatos y metales pesados, asegurando la sostenibilidad del ecosistema acuático recuperado.

Imagen 01: Mina de Touro, 2010.

Imagen 02: Mina de Touro, 2005.

Imagen 03: Mina de Touro, 2002.

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Practice Abstract #10

Synergies between waste valorization and soil remediation

Author: Javier de Rivera Outomuro¹

Objective

Technosols produced for remediating Touro's mine included components such as ashes from combustion of woody debris biomass, produced by the pulp mill from the ENCE factory, together with sewage sludge, residual aluminum gels from aluminum extrusion industries, mussel shell waste, crushed biomass and filler from crushing amphibolite and schist to obtain road aggregates.

Result

On their own, most of these components could be toxic, but adequately mixed in the right proportion make a technosols capable of promoting plant growth and accelerate revegetation in degraded area. These technosols can be applied in the restoration of degraded soils, in agriculture, and in landscaping. This technology presents a sustainable alternative to replace soluble fertilizers, reduce the use of pesticides, restore degraded areas, and provide an environmentally sound destination for both urban and industrial organic and inorganic waste.

Recommendations

The production of technosols involves a scientific process of analysis on the properties of the residues that are used, as well as the composition of the land intervened. Therefore, it has to raise from the collaboration between different social agents, looking to create synergies between universities, industries and land owners. Public development agencies could facilitate these connections by promoting research and shared projects between universities and the industry.

Figure 1. Soil treated with technosols.

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Practice Abstract #10

Sinergias entre la valorización de residuos y la remediación de suelos

Autor: Javier de Rivera Outomuro¹

Objetivo

Los tecnosoles producidos para la remediación de la mina de Touro incluyen componentes como cenizas de la combustión de biomasa de desechos leñosos, producida por la planta de pulpa de la fábrica de ENCE, junto con lodos de depuradora, geles de aluminio residuales de las industrias de extrusión de aluminio, desechos de conchas de mejillón, biomasa triturada y relleno de la trituración de anfíbolita y esquisto para obtener agregados para carreteras.

Resultado

Por sí solos, la mayoría de estos componentes podrían ser tóxicos, pero mezclados en la proporción adecuada forman tecnosoles capaces de promover el crecimiento de las plantas y acelerar la revegetación en áreas degradadas. Estos tecnosoles pueden aplicarse en la restauración de suelos degradados, en la agricultura y en el paisajismo. Esta tecnología presenta una alternativa sostenible para reemplazar los fertilizantes solubles.

Recomendaciones

La producción de tecnosuelos implica un proceso científico de análisis de las propiedades de los residuos que se utilizan, así como de la composición de los terrenos intervenidos. Por ello, debe partir de la colaboración entre diferentes agentes sociales, buscando crear sinergias entre universidades, industrias y propietarios de terrenos. Las agencias públicas de desarrollo podrían facilitar estas conexiones promoviendo investigaciones y proyectos compartidos entre universidades e industria.

Figura 1. Suelo tratado con tecnosoles.

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Lighthouse 4

Practice Abstract #11

Održive prakse gospodarenja tlom na periurbanim poljoprivrednim zemljištima

Autori: Igor Bogunović, Aleksandra Perčin, Marija Galić, Ivan Dugan¹

Cilj

U Zagrebu je poljoprivredna praksa desetljećima ostala nepromijenjena, uz raširenu primjenu pesticida, mineralnih gnojiva i uz minimalni monitoring stanja tla. To je rezultiralo narušavanjem zdravlja tla, zbijanjem tla, erozijom i lošom strukturom tla, osobito u stagnosolima. Izazov je razviti i primijeniti održive poljoprivredne prakse koje se bave ovim problemima, a da istovremeno pospješuju zdravlje i otpornost tla u periurbanim poljoprivrednim područjima.

Rezultati

Prakse gospodarenja tlom, uključujući malčiranje, stalni travnati pokrov i minimalna poremetnja tla, uvedene su u voćnjake jabuka i travnjake. Preliminarni rezultati uzorkovanja tla otkrivaju poboljšanu retenciju vode u tlu na travnjacima u usporedbi s drugim načinima korištenja zemljišta, veću zbijenost na tlima pod jednogodišnjim usjevima i manju zbijenost u šumskom zemljištu. Infiltracija i stabilnost agregata bila je veća u šumskim i travnjačkim tlima, što ukazuje na bolju strukturu tla i smanjen rizik od erozije. Skladištenje ugljika i emisije CO₂ također se pomno prate i najviše su zabilježene u tlima pod travnjacima.

Preporuke

Poljoprivrednici mogu usvojiti metode gospodarenja tlom s malim negativnim utjecajem na tlo, kao što su malčiranje i trajni vegetacijski pokrov, kako bi poboljšali zdravlje tla, retenciju vlage i skladištenje ugljika. Ove prakse mogu smanjiti zbijanje, eroziju i potrebu za kemijskim inputima. Provedbom ovih mjera poboljšat će se otpornost tla, povećati kapacitet za ublažavanje poplava i osigurati održivije korištenje zemljišta u periurbanim područjima. Redovito praćenje stanja tla također je ključno za prilagodbu agrotehničkih praksi na temelju sezonskih varijacija i u odnosu na načine korištenja zemljišta.

Slika 1. Uzorkovanje tla na oranici u Zagrebu.

¹ Sveučilište u Zagrebu Agronomski fakultet, Svetošimunska 25, Zagreb, Hrvatska.

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Practice Abstract #11

Sustainable soil management practices for peri-urban agricultural lands

Authors: Igor Bogunović, Aleksandra Perčin, Marija Galić, Ivan Dugan¹

Objective

In Zagreb, agricultural practices have remained unchanged for decades, with widespread use of pesticides, mineral fertilizers, and minimal soil monitoring. This has led to poor soil health, compaction, erosion, and weak structural stability, particularly in stagnosols. The challenge is to develop and implement sustainable agricultural practices that address these issues while enhancing soil health and resilience in peri-urban agricultural areas.

Result

Soil management practices, including mulching, permanent grass cover, and low soil disturbance, have been introduced in apple orchards and grasslands. Preliminary results from soil sampling reveal improved soil water retention in grasslands compared to other land uses, with higher compaction in cropland and lower compaction in forested areas. Infiltration rates and water-stable aggregates were higher in forest and grassland areas, indicating better soil structure and reduced erosion risk. Carbon storage and CO₂ emissions are also being closely monitored, with emissions highest in grasslands.

Recommendations

Farmers can adopt low-impact soil management techniques, such as mulching and permanent vegetation cover, to improve soil health, water retention, and carbon sequestration. These practices can reduce compaction, erosion, and the need for chemical inputs. Implementing these measures will enhance soil resilience, increase flood mitigation capacity, and ensure more sustainable land use in peri-urban areas. Regular soil monitoring is also crucial for adjusting practices based on seasonal and land-use variations.

Image 1. Soil sampling on cropland in Zagreb.

¹ University of Zagreb Faculty of Agriculture, Svetosimunska 25, Zagreb, Croatia.

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Practice Abstract #12

Poboljšanje zdravlja šumskih i travnjačkih tala u periurbanim područjima

Autori: Igor Bogunović, Aleksandra Perčin, Marija Galić, Ivan Dugan¹

Cilj

Zagrebačka šumska i travnjačka tla sve više su zbijana, sa slabom stabilnošću strukture i podložna su eroziji, što je uzrokovano i prenamjenom prirodne vegetacije u poljoprivredna zemljišta. Cilj je implementirati prakse održivog gospodarenja tlom za šumska i napuštena poljoprivredna zemljišta kako bi se očuvala bioraznolikost, poboljšala struktura tla i povećalo skladištenje ugljika.

Slika 1. Izgled oranice s lošim praksama gospodarenja.

¹ Sveučilište u Zagrebu Agronomski fakultet, Svetošimunska 25, Zagreb, Hrvatska.

Rezultati

Uzorkovanje tla i praćenje utjecaja različitih načina korištenja zemljišta, uključujući šume (asocijacija *Quercus petraea* i *Robinia pseudoacacia*), napuštena poljoprivredna zemljišta i travnjake, sugeriraju na pozitivne rezultate primjene modela održivog gospodarenja. Šumsko zemljište pokazalo je najveću stabilnost agregata, a šumska i travnjačka tla imala su superiorne stope infiltracije vode. Zbijenost tla bila je značajno manja u tim područjima nego na intenzivno gospodarenom poljoprivrednom zemljištu. Emisije CO₂ bile su najveće u travnjacima, što ukazuje na aktivno kruženje ugljika. Ovi rezultati potvrđuju da smanjeno narušavanje tla i prirodni procesi u šumama mogu uvelike poboljšati zdravlje tla.

Preporuke

Osobe koje gospodare zemljištem trebali bi se usredotočiti na minimalno narušavanje tla u šumama i napuštenim poljoprivrednim zemljištima. Promicanjem prirodne razgradnje stabala i lišća pospješit će se struktura tla, povećati infiltracija vode i biološka raznolikost. Osim toga, malčiranje i trajni vegetacijski pokrov na travnjacima mogu dodatno pospješiti zdravlje tla. Te će prakse pridonijeti u održavanju dugoročne stabilnosti ekosustava, poboljšati plodnost tla i potaknuti napore vezane za skladištenjem ugljika, što će pogodovati očuvanju okolišu.

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Slika 2. Perirubana tla s različitim praksama gospodarenja u Zagrebu.

¹ Sveučilište u Zagrebu Agronomski fakultet, Svetošimunska 25, Zagreb, Hrvatska.

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Practice Abstract #12

Enhancing forest and grassland soil health in peri-urban areas

Authors: Igor Bogunović, Aleksandra Perčin, Marija Galić, Ivan Dugan¹

Objective

Zagreb's forest and grassland soils face challenges of compaction, erosion, and poor structural stability, exacerbated by the conversion of natural vegetation to agricultural land. The aim is to implement sustainable soil management practices for forested and abandoned agricultural lands to preserve biodiversity, improve soil structure, and increase carbon sequestration.

Image 1. Look of cropland with bad management practices.

Result

Soil sampling and monitoring across various land uses, including *Quercus petraea* and *Robinia pseudoacacia* forests, abandoned agricultural lands, and grasslands, demonstrated positive outcomes from the application of sustainable management practices. Forest land use showed the highest water-stable aggregate values, and both forest and grassland areas had superior infiltration rates. Soil compaction was significantly lower in these areas than in intensively managed agricultural land, and CO₂ emissions were highest in grasslands, indicating active carbon cycling. These results suggest that reducing soil disturbance and allowing natural decay in forested areas can greatly enhance soil health.

Recommendations

Land managers should focus on minimizing soil disturbance in forests and abandoned agricultural lands. Allowing natural tree and leaf decay can improve soil structure, increase water infiltration, and support biodiversity. Additionally, mulching and permanent vegetation cover in grasslands can further enhance soil health. These practices will help maintain long-term ecosystem stability, improve soil fertility, and boost carbon sequestration efforts, benefiting the environment.

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Image 2. Periurban soils with different management practices in Zagreb.

¹ University of Zagreb Faculty of Agriculture, Svetosimunska 25, Zagreb, Croatia.

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Practice Abstract #13

Urbano planiranje može poboljšati pohranu ugljika i ublažiti učinak poplava

Autori: Igor Bogunović, Aleksandra Perčin, Marija Galić, Ivan Dugan¹

Cilj

Različite načini korištenja zemljišta u zagrebačkim periurbanim područjima utječu na kvalitetu tla i usluge ekosustava. Poljoprivredna praksa u Zagrebu povijesno je uključivala veliku upotrebu pesticida, uzak plodored i nedostatak organskih gnojiva, što je dovelo do narušavanja strukture tla kroz neodrživu zbijenost i eroziju, posebno u praškastim tlima poput Stagnosola. Ova studija imala je za cilj istražiti prakse održivog korištenja zemljišta koje mogu obnoviti zdravlje tla i povećati otpornost na klimatske ekstreme. Analizirana su svojstva tla pod usjevima, travnjacima, napuštenim poljoprivrednim zemljištima, voćnjacima i šumama kako bi se razumio njihov utjecaj na funkcionalnost tla i usluge ekosustava, posebno za kontrolu poplava i skladištenje ugljika.

Preporuke

Kako bi poboljšali kvalitetu oraničnog tla pod usjevima, poljoprivrednici bi trebali razmotriti prakse s malim utjecajem poput malčiranja, trajne vegetacije i konzervacijske obrade tla. Očuvanje šumskih i travnjačkih zemljišta pospješiti će ublažavanje poplava i skladištenje ugljika. Tradicionalne prakse gospodarenja voćnjacima također nude model za održivo korištenje zemljišta, poboljšavajući zdravlje tla i smanjujući rizike od poplava. Redovito praćenje tla i prilagodljivo gospodarenje ključni su za održivo korištenje zemljištem. Ovi napori će promicati otpornost ekosustava, poboljšati strukturu tla i osigurati dugoročne koristi za poljoprivredu i okoliš.

¹ Sveučilište u Zagrebu Agronomski fakultet, Svetošimunska 25, Zagreb, Hrvatska.

Rezultati

Otkrivene su značajne razlike među načinima korištenja zemljišta. Uzorkovanje tla pokazalo je da šume i travnjaci imaju najbolju strukturu tla, s visokom poroznošću, konzervacijom vode i zaliha organskog ugljika. Voćnjaci s malčiranjem i bez obrade imali su umjereno dobre rezultate, dok su intenzivno gospodarene oranice imala veću zbijenost, slabiju konzervaciju vode i smanjenu pohranu organskog ugljika. Šume i travnjaci zabilježili su veću stopu infiltracije i stabilnu strukturu agregata, dok su oranice pod usjevima patili od zbijenosti i općenito niže funkcionalnosti tla. Ova degradacija utječe na bitne usluge ekosustava u periurbanim regijama.

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Smart urban planning can enhance carbon storage and mitigate flood effect

Authors: Igor Bogunović, Aleksandra Perčin, Marija Galić, Ivan Dugan¹

Objective

Different land uses in Zagreb peri-urban areas affect soil quality and ecosystem services. Agricultural practices in Zagreb historically included heavy pesticide use, narrow crop rotation and absence of organic fertilizers, leading to soil structural deterioration manifested in unsustainable soil compaction, and erosion, especially in silty soils like Stagnosols. This case study aimed to explore sustainable land use practices that can restore soil health and increase resilience to climate extremes. Soil properties in cropland, grassland, abandoned agricultural, orchard, and forest areas were analyzed to understand their impact on soil functionality and ecosystem services, particularly for flood control and carbon storage.

Result

Findings reveal significant differences among land uses. Soil sampling showed that forests and grasslands have the best soil structure, with high porosity, water retention, and organic carbon stocks. Orchards with mulch and no-tillage performed moderately well, while intensive managed croplands had more compacted soils, lower water retention, and reduced organic carbon. Forest and grassland areas exhibited higher infiltration rates and stable aggregate structure, while croplands suffered from compaction and reduced soil functionality. This degradation impacts essential ecosystem services in peri-urban regions.

Recommendations

To enhance soil quality in croplands, farmers should consider low-impact practices like mulching, permanent vegetation, and conservation tillage. Preserving forested and grassland areas will support flood mitigation and carbon sequestration. Traditional orchard management practices also offer a model for sustainable land use, enhancing soil health and mitigating flood risks. Regular soil monitoring and adaptive management are critical for sustainable land use. These efforts will promote ecosystem resilience, improve soil structure, and provide long-term benefits for both agriculture and the environment.

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Lighthouse 5

Practice Abstract #14

Baltupiai urban gardens soil quality recovery

Authors: Pereira Paulo, Katarzyna Bogdzevic, Miguel Inacio, Marija Meišutovič-Akhtarieva¹

Objective

Most of gardens in Baltupiai are surrounded individual houses. Other land uses are grassland, park or lawn. Many gardeners have stopped planting fruits and vegetables and arranged lawns. The main issues identified with soil were:

- Poor land use (use of agrochemicals and intensive production).
- flooding regulation.
- Erosion.

Result

Translating this information in ecosystems services assessment, the lawn has a lower capacity for flood regulation, carbon sequestration and erosion regulation than the other land uses. Urban park was the land use with the highest capacity for flood regulation, and urban gardens had the highest values of carbon sequestration.

Recommendations

Increase the use of land with highest capacity for flood regulation and highest values of carbon sequestration, for example the lawn or urban park land.

¹ Mykolas Romeris University Laboratories (MRU LAB).

Practice Abstract #14

Baltupių miesto sodų dirvožemio kokybės atkūrimas

Autoriai: Pereira Paulo, Katarzyna Bogdzevic, Miguel Inacio, Marija Meišutovič-Akhtarjeva¹

Tikslas

Dauguma Baltupių sodų yra apsupti individualių namų. Kiti žemės naudojimo būdai apima pievas, parkus arba vejas. Daugelis sodininkų nustojo sodinti vaisius ir daržoves ir įsirengė vejas. Pagrindinės su dirvožemiu susijusios problemos buvo šios:

- prastas žemės naudojimas (agrochemikalų naudojimas ir intensyvi gamyba).
- potvynių reguliavimas.
- Erozija.

Rezultatas

Vertinant ekosistemų paslaugas, veja turi mažesnę pajėgumą reguliuoti potvynius, sulaikyti anglį ir reguliuoti eroziją, palyginti su kitais žemės naudojimo būdais. Miesto parkas buvo žemės naudojimo būdas, turintis didžiausią potvynių reguliavimo pajėgumą, o miesto sodai pasižymėjo didžiausia anglies sulaikymo verte.

Rekomendacijos

Didinti žemės naudojimą, turinčią didžiausią potvynių reguliavimo pajėgumą ir didžiausias anglies sulaikymo vertes, pavyzdžiui, veją arba miesto parko žemę.

¹ Mykolas Romeris University Laboratories (MRU LAB).

Practice Abstract #15

Management of urban lawns

Authors: Pereira Paulo, Katarzyna Bogdzevic, Miguel Inacio, Marija Meišutovič-Akhtarjeva¹

Objective

The objective is to understand the impacts of management on lawns ecosystem services supply, namely flood regulation and pollination.

Result

Lawns supply a wide range of ecosystem services. These areas are often neglected . In addition to this, there are areas with an incorrect management (e.g., very frequent mowing) and places where the litter pollution is high. The areas that are less mowed and vegetation has a better quality are the ones that have a high capacity for flood regulation and pollination.

Recommendations

It is important that the local authorities reduce the lawns mowing frequency during spring and summer because this can reduce the pollination and flood regulation capacity.

¹ Mykolas Romeris University Laboratories (MRU LAB).

Practice Abstract #15

Miesto vejų tvarkymas

Autoriai: Pereira Paulo, Katarzyna Bogdzevic, Miguel Inacio, Marija Meišutovič-Akhtarjeva¹

Tikslas

Tikslas - išsiaiškinti vejų tvarkymo poveikį jų teikiamoms ekosisteminiams paslaugoms, t. y. potvynių reguliavimui ir apdulkinimui.

Rezultatas

Vejos teikia daugybę ekosisteminių paslaugų. Tačiau šie plotai dažnai būna apleisti. Be to, yra teritorijų, kurios netinkamai tvarkomos (pvz., labai dažnai šienaujamos), ir vietų, kuriose kaupiasi daug šiukšlių. Teritorijos, kuriose mažiau šienaujama, o augmenija yra geresnės kokybės, pasižymi dideliu potvynių reguliavimo ir apdulkinimo gebėjimu.

Rekomendacijos

Svarbu, kad vietos valdžios institucijos pavasarį ir vasarą sumažintų vejų šienavimo dažnumą, nes dažnas šienavimas gali sumažinti apdulkinimo ir potvynių reguliavimo galimybes.

¹ Mykolas Romeris University Laboratories (MRU LAB).

Practice Abstract #16

Vegetation management impact on thermal properties in urban park on climate regulation

Authors: Pereira Paulo, Katarzyna Bogdzevic, Miguel Inacio, Marija Meišutovič-Akhtarieva¹

Objective

The objective of this work is to assess the impact of urban parks on microclimate regulation

Result

Urban parks normally function as cold islands in urban areas. They are important to contra balance the impact of concrete in urban climate. In the park studied, the temperature compared with the surrounding urban areas and lawns. This is especially important during the summer, where urban parks have a high importance on microclimate regulation.

Recommendations

It is key for local authorities that parks be well managed and with the necessary infrastructure to be used. They are places that persons can use to reduce the heat stress during summer periods because they are places where the population can be comfortable.

¹ Mykolas Romeris University Laboratories (MRU LAB).

Practice Abstract #16

Augalijos tvarkymo poveikis šiluminėms savybėms miesto parke ir jo vaidmuo klimato reguliavime

Autoriai: Pereira Paulo, Katarzyna Bogdzevic, Miguel Inacio, Marija Meišutovič-Akhtarieva¹

Tikslas

Tikslas - įvertinti miesto parkų poveikį mikroklimato reguliavimui.

Rezultatas

Miestų parkai paprastai veikia kaip šaltosios salos miestų teritorijose. Jie yra itin svarbūs subalansuojant betono poveikį miesto klimatui. Tirtame parke temperatūra, palyginti su aplinkinėmis miesto teritorijomis ir vejomis, buvo žemesnė. Tai ypač svarbu vasarą, kai miestų parkai atlieka reikšmingą vaidmenį mikroklimato reguliavime.

Rekomendacijos

Vietos valdžios institucijoms labai svarbu užtikrinti, kad parkai būtų tinkamai tvarkomi ir aprūpinti reikalinga infrastruktūra. Šios erdvės suteikia žmonėms galimybę sumažinti karščio keliamą stresą vasaros laikotarpiais, nes tai yra vietos, kuriose gyventojai gali jaustis gerai.

¹ Mykolas Romeris University Laboratories (MRU LAB).

Lighthouse 6

Practice Abstract #17

Forest fertilization sustainability

Author: Dagnija Lazdina ¹

Objective

Forest fertilization, or improving tree growth conditions - ensuring optimal light conditions and sufficient amounts of macro and micro elements as well as soil pH, so that plant nutrients are in forms available to plants. The frequency and intensity of nutrient deficiency symptoms depend on the age of the forest stands, soil type, tree species and, often, also on the moisture regime. The forester must be able to identify signs of nutrient deficiency and, if possible, also take measures to improve growing conditions in order to prevent nutrient deficiency.

Result

First of all, it is necessary to choose tree species suitable for the respective conditions. A deficiency situation can also develop over time in initially sufficiently fertile soils, for example, in spruce stands on peat soils, as the biomass of woody plants increases, soil potassium reserves may be depleted or, as the growth conditions change (the groundwater level rises), the reserves of nutrients available to plants decrease. A pilot trial of the introduction of additional nutritional elements has resulted in an increase in the volume of wood by 10-15 m³ over five years. In spruce and deciduous stands, the response is observed faster than in pine stands, which are less demanding in terms of growth conditions.

Recommendations

If there is a lack or imbalance of plant nutrients, fertilizer is an effective solution to bring missing nutrients into the ecosystem and ensure favorable conditions for the development of woody plants in the forest stand. Forest fertilization is also an effective means of reducing the impact of human economic activity by returning nutrients removed with timber and biofuels to the forest after thinning, management or final felling.

¹ Latvian State Forest Research Institute "Silava" & The Forest Research Station.

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Practice Abstract #17

Ilgstspējīga mežaudžu mēslošana

Autori: Dagnija Lazdina ¹

Mērķi

Meža mēslošana jeb koku augšanas apstākļu uzlabošana - nodrošinot optimālus gaismas apstākļus un pietiekamu daudzumu makro un mikroelementu, kā arī augšnes pH, lai augu barības elementi būtu augiem pieejamās formās. Barības vielu deficīta simptomu biežums un intensitāte ir atkarīga no mežaudžu vecuma, augšnes veida, koku sugām un bieži vien arī no mitruma režīma. Mežsaimniekam jāspēj noteikt barības vielu deficīta pazīmes un, ja iespējams, arī jāveic pasākumi augšanas apstākļu uzlabošanai, lai nienestu audzēs koku augšanai nepieciešamos elementus.

Leteikumi

Ja ir augu barības vielu trūkums vai nelīdzsvarotība, mēslojums ir efektīvs risinājums, lai ekosistēmā ienestu trūkstošās barības vielas un nodrošinātu mežaudzē labvēlīgus apstākļus kokaugu attīstībai. Meža mēslošana ir arī efektīvs līdzeklis cilvēku saimnieciskās darbības ietekmes mazināšanai, atgriežot mežā ar kokmateriāliem un biodegvielu izņemtās barības vielas pēc retināšanas, apsaimniekošanas vai atjaunošanas circes.

Rezultāti

Vispirms ir jāizvēlas attiecīgajiem apstākļiem piemērotas koku sugas. Deficīta situācija ar laiku var veidoties arī sākotnēji pietiekami auglīgās augsnēs, piemēram, egļu audzēs uz kūdras augsnēm, palielinoties koksnes augu biomasai, var izsīkt augšnes kālija rezerves vai, mainoties augšanas apstākļiem (paaugstinās gruntsūdens līmenis), samazinās augiem pieejamās barības vielu rezerves. Papildu barošanās elementu ieviešanas izmēģinājuma rezultātā koksnes apjoms piecu gadu laikā ir palielinājies par 10-15 m³. Egļu un lapu koku audzēs reakcija novērojama ātrāk nekā priežu audzēs, kas augšanas apstākļu ziņā ir mazāk prasīgas.

¹ Latvian State Forest Research Institute "Silava" & The Forest Research Station.

Practice Abstract #18

Mining site recultivation

Author: Dagnija Lazdina ¹

Objective

The plantations were established with the aim of demonstrating quarry reclamation, after leveling the territory, by establishing tree stands with different technologies in different designs. In the long term, to find out what results can be obtained by planting tree species with different requirements for soil fertility and aeration, moisture regime. to evaluate tree growth at different distances with the Nelder wheel model.

Result

The provision of nutrients is related to the mechanical and mineralogical composition of the soil. If the soil was formed by the decomposition of granite, phosphorus will be needed, but if the bedrock is dolomite, then potassium fertilizer will be needed. Soils formed from sandstone usually have insufficient amounts of all major nutrients. Peat soils are acidic. A larger amount of fine particles improves the availability of elements to tree roots, increases moisture capacity and adsorption of mineral fertilizers. In forestry, soil analyses do not always show a correlation between nutrient availability and tree growth, this can be explained by the symbiosis of trees and fungi, which probably allows for the use of more nutrients; the amount of active nutrients is also characterized by seasonal fluctuations related to plant consumption and the activity of microorganisms.

Recommendations

Nutrient deficiencies are common in non-forest soils, such as afforested marginal agricultural lands, gravel and sand mine, and reclaimed peatlands. Therefore, preventive measures should include soil improvement and the establishment of vegetation suitable for tree plantations to reduce the impact of wind and water erosion. Mulching of planted trees is recommended.

¹ Latvian State Forest Research Institute "Silava" & The Forest Research Station.

Practice Abstract #18

Derīgo izrakteņu ieguves vietu rekultivācija

Autori: Dagnija Lazdina ¹

Mērķi

Stādījumi izveidoti ar mērķi demonstrēt karjeru rekultivāciju, pēc teritorijas izlīdzināšanas, ierīkojot koku audzes ar dažādām tehnoloģijām un dažādos dizainos. Ilgtermiņā noskaidrot, kādus rezultātus var iegūt, stādot koku sugas ar dažādām prasībām augsnes auglībai un aerācijai, mitruma režīmam. Novērtēt koku augšanu dažādos attālumos ar Nelder apļu modeli.

Rezultāti

Barības vielu nodrošināšana ir saistīta ar augsnes mehānisko un mineralogisko sastāvu. Ja augsne veidojusies, sadaloties granītam, būs nepieciešams fosfors, bet, ja pamatieži ir dolomīts, tad būs nepieciešams kālija mēslojums. Augsnēs, kas veidojas no smilšakmens, parasti ir nepietiekams visu galveno barības vielu daudzums. Kūdras augsnes ir skābas. Lielāks smalko daļiņu daudzums uzlabo elementu pieejamību koku saknēm, palielina mitruma spēju un minerālmēslu adsorbciju. Mežsaimniecībā augsnes analīzes ne vienmēr parāda korelāciju starp barības vielu pieejamību un koku augšanu, tas skaidrojams ar koku un sēņu simbiozi, kas, iespējams, ļauj izmantot vairāk barības vielu; aktīvo barības vielu daudzumu raksturo arī sezonālās svārstības, kas saistītas ar augu patēriņu un mikroorganismu aktivitāti.

Leteikumi

Barības vielu deficīts ir izplatīts augsnēs, kas nav mežs, piemēram, apmežotās marginālās lauksaimniecības zemēs, smilts un grants raktuvēs un rekultivētos kūdrājos. Tāpēc jau profilaktiski jāparedz augsnes uzlabošana un koku stādījumiem piemērotas veģetācijas ierīkošana, lai samazinātu vēja un ūdens erozijas ietekmi. Iestādīto koku mulčēšana arī ir ieteicama.

¹ Latvian State Forest Research Institute "Silava" & The Forest Research Station.

Practice Abstract #19

Forest regeneration practices- importance of planting site

Author: Dagnija Lazdina ¹

Objective

The impact of planting site creation on soil health - wind and rainwater erosion on slopes and valleys, as well as the importance of planting site type on the growth of planted trees - root system formation and tree survival are topics of the research in the Mežole region's new foreststands.

Result

Young stands are renewed by preparing the soil or planting spot for seedling. On steep slopes, the soil and the seeds that have fallen on it in the winter are washed away, therefore planting is the solution. In valleys, the soil is prepared by forming a mound. In Latvian conditions, a mound is primarily a more suitable place for seedlings to create a drier place, and the double, folded layer of humus as a source of nutrients is of secondary importance. The pit next to the mound acts as a water accumulator and collector, depending on the amount of precipitation, on the mound roots form in all directions, while in the furrow only parallel to it. Monitoring of GHG is carried out in FRS.

Recommendations

Furrows are a suitable planting site in dry flat areas, on slopes they act as micro-ravines, organic matter washes away, water exposes plant roots. Therefore on slopes furrows should be made obliquely to reduce the speed of water movement. In areas with uneven terrain, mound formation is a solution for creating suitable planting sites by varying the height of the mound, or even planting in a scarified area, on the top of a hill. If the groundwater level is too high, the roots are shallow and become easily damaged in adulthood - wind-unresistant.

¹ Latvian State Forest Research Institute "Silava" & The Forest Research Station.

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Practice Abstract #19

Meža atjaunošanas– stādīšanas vietas nozīme

Autori: Dagnija Lazdina ¹

Mērķi

Stādīšanas vietas izveides ietekmē augsnes veselību - vēja un lietus ūdens erozija nogāzēs un ielejās, kā arī stādīšanas vietas veidam ir būtiska nozīme stādīto koku augšanā- sakņu sistēmas veidošanās un koku izdzīvošana ir viens no pētījumu objektiem Mežoles jaunaudzēs.

Rezultāti

Jaunaudzes atjaunojot, sagatavo t augsni vai stādīšanas vietu jaunajam kokam. Stāvās nogāzēs augsne un ziemā uz tās nobirusās sēklas tiek izskalotas, tāpēcpiemērots risinājums ir stādīšana nevis sēšana. Ielejās augsni sagatavo, veidojot pilskalnu. Latvijas apstākļos pacila ir primāri piemērotāka vieta stādiem, lai izveidotu sausāku vietu, un dubultā, "salocītai" trūdvielu kārtai kā barības vielu avotam ir sekundāra nozīme. Blakus pacilai esošā bedre ,atkarībā no nokrišņu daudzuma, darbojas kā ūdens uzkrājējs un savācējs, pacilās saknes veidojas visos virzienos, savukārt vagā galvenokārt paralēli tai. Meža pētīšanas stacijas jaunaudzēs tiek veikts SEG monitorings.

Leteikumi

Vagas ir piemērota stādīšanas vieta sausās, līdzenās vietās, bet nogāzēs tās darbojas kā mikrogravas, organiskās vielas izskalojas, ūdens atsedz augu saknes. Tāpēc nogāzēs vagas jāveido slīpi, lai samazinātu ūdens kustības ātrumu. Vietās ar nelīdzenu reljefu, pacilu veidošana ir risinājums, kā izveidot piemērotas stādīšanas vietas, mainot piacilas augstumu vai pat stādot skarificētā vietā, kalna galā. Ja gruntsūdens līmenis ir pārāk augsts, saknes ir sekla un pieaugušā vecumā kļūst viegli bojājamas – vēja neizturīgas.

¹ Latvian State Forest Research Institute "Silava" & The Forest Research Station.

Lighthouse 7

Practice Abstract #20

Diverse groenbemester mengsels

Autori: Linda Calciolari, André Jurrius ¹

Objectief

Deze praktijk is een essentieel onderdeel van onze geïntegreerde aanpak voor het beheren van bodemgezondheid en productiviteit op de boerderij. We hebben verschillende doelen:

- 1-Ondersteunen van een diverse gemeenschap van bodemmicro-organismen die de plantgezondheid bevorderen.
- 2-Voorkomen van nutriëntenverlies door uitspoeling.
- 3-Verbeteren van de bodemstructuur.
- 4-Verhogen van het organische stofgehalte in de bodem.
- 5-Stikstof binden. Afhankelijk van de specifieke uitdagingen van het seizoen leggen we de nadruk op één of meer van deze doelen.

De basis van onze groenbemestingsmix bestaat uit een combinatie gewassen uit de kool-familie (bijv. mosterd), de grassen-familie (bijv. granen) en de vlinderbloemige-familie (bijv. klaver).

Resultaat

De resultaten zijn niet systematisch gemonitord, maar eerder geobserveerd in de context van agronomische praktijken. Uit wetenschappelijke literatuur die mengsels van groenbemesters (drie soorten) vergelijkt met monoculturen, halen we de volgende bevindingen. Gemiddeld genomen produceren mengsels meer biomassa en leveren ze meer stikstof dan monoculturen (Elhakeem et al., 2019). Mengsels van groenbemesters hebben ook het potentieel om meer stikstof in de bodem vast te houden en uitspoeling aanzienlijk te verminderen in vergelijking met monoculturen. Dit effect is echter sterk afhankelijk van de specifieke soorten die in het mengsel worden gekozen. Snelgroeïende groenbemesters en mengsels zijn het meest effectief in het onderdrukken van onkruid, waarbij kruisbloemige soorten bijzonder geschikt zijn voor dit doel (Elhakeem, 2021).

¹ Ekoboerderij de Lingehof: Het is een biologisch en biodynamisch akkerbouwbedrijf in Nederland van 130 hectare. Ze produceren meer dan 10 verschillende groente- en graangewassen en experimenteren met regeneratieve landbouw.

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Aanbevelingen

- 1- Definieer duidelijk de belangrijkste doelen die je wilt bereiken met groenbemesters. De keuze van soorten in je mengsel is sterk afhankelijk van deze doelen.
- 2- Zorg ervoor dat je mengsel ten minste één soort uit de grassenfamilie (zoals granen), een vlinderbloemige (bijv. klover) en een brassica (bijv. mosterd) bevat, tenzij één van deze een negatief effect heeft op het doel dat je wilt bereiken.
- 3- Planten hebben verschillende wortelsystemen; het is interessant om combinaties te maken die elkaar aanvullen op dit gebied.
- 4- Een sterke, winterharde groenbemester biedt veel voordelen, maar vereist tijd om in het voorjaar te beëindigen. Dit kan lastig zijn tijdens een nat voorjaar. Houd dit in gedachten als een potentiële risicofactor.

Bedek het gewasmengsel met onder meer zonnebloem, boekweit, mosterd, lijnzaad, radijs, klover en granen.

¹ Ekoboerderij de Lingehof: Het is een biologisch en biodynamisch akkerbouwbedrijf in Nederland van 130 hectare. Ze produceren meer dan 10 verschillende groente- en graangewassen en experimenteren met regeneratieve landbouw.

Practice Abstract #20

Diverse cover crop mixes

Authors: Linda Calciolari, André Jurrius ¹

Objective

This practice is a crucial component of our integrated approach to managing soil health and farm productivity. We have several objectives:

- 1-Support a diverse community of soil microorganisms that, in turn, benefits plant health.
- 2-Prevent nutrient loss through leaching.
- 3-Improve soil structure.
- 4-Increase organic matter content in the soil.
- 5-Fix nitrogen.
- 6-Protect the soil in the winter. Depending on the specific challenges of the season, we focus on one or more of these objectives.

The base of our green manures mix is a combination of crops from the cabbage family (e.g. mustard), grass family (e.g. cereals) and pea-family (clover).

Result

The results have not been systematically monitored but have instead been observed in the context of agronomic practices. However, from scientific literature comparing green manure mixtures (three species) with monocultures, we have gathered the following insights. On average, mixtures tend to produce more biomass and yield higher nitrogen levels than monocultures (Elhakeem et al., 2019). Cover crop mixtures also have the potential to retain more nitrogen in the soil and significantly reduce leaching compared to monocultures. However, this effect largely depends on the specific species selected for the mixture. Fast-establishing cover crops and mixtures are the most effective at suppressing weeds, with cruciferous species being particularly suitable for this purpose (Elhakeem, 2021).

¹ Ekoboerderij de Lingehof: It is a 130 hectares organic and biodynamic arable farm in the Netherlands. They produce more than 10 different vegetable and cereal crops and experiment with regenerative farming.

Recommendations

1-Clearly define the main goals you wish to achieve with green manures. The choice of species in your mix depends heavily on these goals.

2-Ensure your mix includes at least one species from the grass family (such as cereals), a legume (e.g., clover), and a brassica (e.g., mustard), unless one of these has a negative effect on your specific objective.

3-Different plants have varying root systems; it's beneficial to combine species that complement each other in this regard.

4-A vigorous, winter-hardy cover crop offers many advantages but requires time to terminate in the spring, which can be challenging during a wet spring.

Consider this a potential risk factor.

Cover crop mix including sunflower, buckwheat, mustard, linseed, fodder radish, clover and cereals.

¹ Ekoboerderij de Lingehof: It is a 130 hectares organic and biodynamic arable farm in the Netherlands. They produce more than 10 different vegetable and cereal crops and experiment with regenerative farming.

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Practice Abstract #21

Bodemopbouwende vruchtwisseling

Autori: Linda Calciolari, André Jurrius ¹

Objectief

Het doel is om de bodemgezondheid, -structuur, -vruchtbaarheid en biodiversiteit op de lange termijn te verbeteren en te behouden door een geplande afwisseling van verschillende gewassen. Belangrijke doelen zijn:

- 1-Langdurige productiviteit door verbeterde bodemstructuur en -vruchtbaarheid.
- 2-Verminderen van de behoefte aan inputs en het verbeteren van de inputefficiëntie door planten.
- 3-Onderdrukken van onkruid, plagen en ziekten.
- 4-Verhogen van de biodiversiteit en verminderen van de impact op het milieu.

Resultaat

Geïntegreerd met andere praktijken, deze gewasrotatie heeft geleid tot een enorme vermindering van de behoefte aan (organische) meststoffen, van 170 kg/N per hectare tot gemiddeld ongeveer 70 kg/N per hectare. De algehele bodemkwaliteit op het bedrijf is ook verbeterd. Dit kunnen we visueel beoordelen elke keer dat we in de grond graven: we zien een grote hoeveelheid regenwormen, fijne wortels en een 'kruimelige' bodemstructuur in de meeste percelen. Dit is ook zichtbaar in de bodemtests.

¹ Ekoboerderij de Lingehof: Het is een biologisch en biodynamisch akkerbouwbedrijf in Nederland van 130 hectare. Ze produceren meer dan 10 verschillende groente- en graangewassen en experimenteren met regeneratieve landbouw.

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Een voorbeeld van een bodemopbouwende vruchtwisseling, gebaseerd op de ervaring van Ekoboerderij de Lingehof.

Aanbevelingen

Belangrijke overwegingen:

- Minimaal een 1:6 gewasrotatie.
- Wissel "rustgewassen" (granen en stikstofbinders) af met intensievere gewassen.
- Minimaal 15% van de gewassen moet stikstofbindend zijn, waarvan één een langer blijvend gewas (zoals gras-klover of luzerne).

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Practice Abstract #21

Soil building crop rotation

Authors: Linda Calciolari, André Jurrius ¹

Objective

The objective is to improve and maintain soil health, structure, fertility, and biodiversity over time through a planned sequence of different crops. Key goals include:

- 1-Long term productivity by improved soil structure and fertility.
- 2-Reduce the need for inputs and the input use efficiency by plants.
- 3-Suppress weeds, pests, and diseases.
- 4-Enhance biodiversity and reduce impact on the environment.

Result

Integrated with other practices, this crop rotation has resulted in a tremendous reduction in the need for (organic) manure input (from 170 to about 70 kg/N ha on average). The overall soil quality at the farm has also improved, we can assess this visually every time we dig in the soil and see a large amount of rainworms, fine roots and a 'crumbly' soil structure in the soil in most plots. This is also visible in the soil tests.

¹ Ekoboerderij de Lingehof: It is a 130 hectares organic and biodynamic arable farm in the Netherlands. They produce more than 10 different vegetable and cereal crops and experiment with regenerative farming.

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An example of a soil building crop rotation based on the experience of Ekoboerderij de Lingehof in the Netherlands.

Recommendations

Our key considerations are:

- Minimum 1:6 crop rotation.
- Alternate “resting” crops (cereals and N-fixers) with cash crops.
- Include at least 15% N.
- Fixing crops of which a longer lasting crop (e.g. grass-clover or alfalfa).

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Practice Abstract #22

Johnson-Su composteren

Autori: Linda Calciolari, André Jurrius ¹

Objectief

De Johnson-Su compostmethoden is een vorm van aerobe compostering met als primaire doel het creëren van hoogwaardige, biologisch actieve compost. De methode richt zich op het bevorderen van een diverse gemeenschap van nuttige micro-organismen, met name schimmels, die een cruciale rol spelen bij het opbouwen van de bodemstructuur, het verbeteren van de nutriëntenkringloop en het bevorderen van de plantengezondheid. Schimmels kunnen bovendien minder goed tegen landbouwactiviteiten dan bacteriële gemeenschappen.

Voorbeeld van een opstelling voor het maken van Johnson-Su compost met behulp van een IBC-kooi met een geperforeerde bodem.

Resultaat

Productie van hoogwaardige schimmelcompost die kan worden gebruikt voor het brouwen van compostthee en extracten voor bodem-inoculatie. Deze producten zijn rijk aan nuttige micro-organismen en voedingsstoffen, wat de bodemgezondheid verbetert en de plantengroei bevordert.

De effecten van compostthee en de optimale toepassingsmethoden worden echter nog onderzocht. Lopende studies zijn gericht op het maximaliseren van de voordelen van deze producten voor verschillende gewassen en bodemomstandigheden, om een effectieve toepassing in duurzame landbouw te waarborgen.

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Aanbevelingen

- 1-Overweeg het gebruik van IBC-containers met geperforeerde bodems in plaats van het originele cilindrische ontwerp voor eenvoudigere installatie en opslag.
- 2-Streef naar een C/N-verhouding van 30:1.
- 3-Het vochtgehalte moet gedurende het proces op 60% worden gehouden.
- 4-Controleer de temperatuur in de eerste weken om ziekteverwekkers te beheersen.
- 5-Voeg compostwormen (na een aantal maanden) toe om de afbraak en de beschikbaarheid van voedingsstoffen te verbeteren.
- 6-Het composteerproces duurt ongeveer 12 maanden om rijpe compost te produceren.
- 7-Test de resulterende compost door middel van microscopische evaluatie en/of met een kiemtest.

Schimmels ontwikkelen zich op de composthoop.

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Practice Abstract #22

Johnson-Su composting

Authors: Linda Calciolari, André Jurrius ¹

Objective

The Johnson-Su composting method, is a form of aerobic composting with the primary goal of creating high-quality, biologically active compost. The method focuses on fostering a diverse community of beneficial microorganisms, particularly fungi, which play a crucial role in building soil structure, enhancing nutrient cycling, and improving plant health and which can tolerate less well agricultural activities than bacterial communities.

Layout of a possible setup to make Johnson-Su compost using an IBC cage with a perforated bottom.

Result

Availability of high-quality fungal compost that can be brewed into compost tea and extracts for soil inoculation. These products are rich in beneficial microorganisms and nutrients, enhancing soil health and promoting plant growth.

The effects of compost tea and optimal application methods are still under research. Ongoing studies aim to maximize the benefits of these products for various crops and soil conditions, ensuring their effective use in sustainable farming.

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Recommendations

- 1-Consider using IBC cages with perforated bottoms instead of the original cylindrical design for easier setup and storage.
- 2-Aim for a C/N ratio of 30:1.
- 3-Moisture content should be kept at 60% throughout the process.
- 4-Monitor temperature in the first weeks to ensure pathogen control.
- 5-After the temperature has stabilised (takes a couple months) incorporate composting worms to enhance decomposition and nutrient availability.
- 6-The composting process takes about 12 months to produce mature compost.
- 7-Test the resulting compost by means of a microscope evaluation and/or with a germination test.

Fungi develop on the compost heap.

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Living Lab 1

Practice Abstract #23

Conservation agriculture for sustainability cereal systems in the Mediterranean

Authors: Gianluca Carboni ¹, Valentina Mereu ²

Objective

Soil fertility and health in the Mediterranean region are deteriorating due to intensive agricultural practices and increasingly challenging environmental conditions driven by climate change. This degradation threatens the ecosystem services that healthy soils provide, ultimately diminishing agricultural profitability and leading to the abandonment of cultivated land. Conservation agriculture offers one of the most promising solutions to address these challenges. It incorporates a set of practices focused on conserving water and soil through reduced soil disturbance, permanent soil cover, and crop rotations. These three principles—the pillars of conservation agriculture—not only enhance the resilience of cereal-based systems to climate change but also lower greenhouse gas emissions from agricultural activities, thereby helping farmers maintain stable incomes.

Result

The adoption of conservation tillage in cereal systems within the Mediterranean region has demonstrated that yields remain comparable to those under conventional management, while significantly reducing farm management costs in terms of time and resources, even in the early years of adoption. This practice also leads to substantial environmental benefits. Besides reducing fossil fuel consumption, long-term benefits include increased soil organic matter content, improved fertility, and increased water retention capacity, especially during dry seasons. These benefits enable cereal systems managed with conservation techniques to adapt to climate change and become more sustainable, through lower emissions and increased soil carbon stocks. Furthermore, the reduced costs make this approach a practical solution, even in low-productivity areas prone to potential abandonment.

¹ Agricultural research agency of Sardinia (AGRIS)

² Euro Mediterranean Centre on Climate Change Foundation (CMCC)

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Recommendations

Conservation agriculture offers multiple benefits but it requires careful soil and crop management, including timely planting, optimal control of weeds and crop residues, and careful selection of species and varieties to be included in the rotations' schemes. Optimal management requires continuous up-to-date training and knowledge exchange, including information on funding opportunities.

CONSERVATION AGRICULTURE

Figure 1: The three pillars of conservation agriculture

¹ Agricultural research agency of Sardinia (AGRIS)

² Euro Mediterranean Centre on Climate Change Foundation (CMCC)

Practice Abstract #23

Agricoltura conservativa per la sostenibilità dei sistemi cerealicoli nel Mediterraneo

Autori: Gianluca Carboni ¹, Valentina Mereu ²

Obiettivo

La fertilità e la salute dei suoli nell'area del Mediterraneo sta peggiorando a causa della gestione intensiva dei sistemi agricoli e alle condizioni ambientali meno favorevoli connesse ai cambiamenti climatici mettendo a rischio i servizi ecosistemici che un suolo sano può fornire. Ciò comporta una riduzione della redditività delle attività agricole e favorire l'abbandono delle terre coltivate. L'agricoltura conservativa è tra le pratiche agricole più promettenti per rispondere a queste sfide in quanto include un insieme di tecniche finalizzate alla conservazione dell'acqua e del suolo attraverso la riduzione del "disturbo del suolo", la "gestione dei residui colturali" e gli "avvicendamenti colturali". Questi tre concetti, che costituiscono i pilastri dell'agricoltura conservativa, contribuiscono sia ad aumentare l'adattamento dei sistemi cerealicoli ai cambiamenti climatici sia a ridurre le emissioni di gas serra in atmosfera, favorendo l'ottenimento di redditi stabili per gli agricoltori.

Risultato

L'applicazione delle lavorazioni conservative in sistemi cerealicoli in areale Mediterraneo ha evidenziato l'ottenimento di rese simili alla gestione convenzionale a fronte di una riduzione dei costi legati alla gestione aziendale in termini di tempo e risorse dedicate alle operazioni colturali già durante i primi anni di applicazione, con effetti positivi anche dal punto di vista ambientale. Oltre alla riduzione dell'utilizzo di combustibili fossili, nel lungo periodo sono stati osservati benefici legati all'incremento del contenuto di sostanza organica del suolo, migliore fertilità e capacità di conservare l'acqua soprattutto in annate siccitose. Questo ha permesso un migliore adattamento dei sistemi cerealicoli gestiti in con tecniche conservative e una maggiore sostenibilità degli stessi legata alle minori emissioni e all'aumentato stoccaggio del carbonio nel suolo. Inoltre, i minori costi la rendono una soluzione razionale anche in aree poco produttive e soggette a potenziale abbandono.

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Raccomandazioni

L'agricoltura conservativa ha molti benefici ma richiede attenzione nella sua applicazione con accorgimenti legati a una tempestiva gestione delle semine, un'attenta gestione delle infestanti e dei residui colturali e un'ottimale scelta delle specie e varietà e da inserire nelle rotazioni. Una gestione ottimale richiede una formazione continua e aggiornata e lo scambio di conoscenze, anche in riferimento alle opportunità di finanziamento.

AGRICOLTURA CONSERVATIVA

Figura 1: I tre pilastri dell'agricoltura conservativa

¹ Agricultural research agency of Sardinia (AGRIS)

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Practice Abstract #24

Lavorazioni conservative e carbonio nel suolo

Autori: Gianluca Carboni ¹, Valentina Mereu ²

Obiettivo

La fertilità e la salute dei suoli nell'area del Mediterraneo sta peggiorando a causa delle condizioni ambientali sempre meno favorevoli, anche a causa dei cambiamenti climatici in corso con siccità, ondate di calore e alluvioni più intense e frequenti. La gestione convenzionale delle colture con lavorazioni profonde e frequenti comporta un impoverimento di sostanza organica e carbonio dei suoli che risultano meno fertili e con stabilità degli aggregati inferiore che determina una maggiore suscettibilità ai fenomeni erosivi. Per limitare questi fenomeni sono state studiate le tecniche di lavorazione conservative che hanno lo scopo di conservare acqua e suolo. Le lavorazioni conservative perseguono la riduzione del "disturbo del suolo". Questa, associata alla "gestione dei residui colturali", consente di proteggere la superficie del suolo dall'erosione e di aumentare il suo contenuto di sostanza organica nel tempo.

Risultato

Riducendo le lavorazioni e disturbando meno il suolo, esso diventa più compatto e meno ossigenato (fig. 1) e questo consente una riduzione della mineralizzazione della sostanza organica (fig. 2). Questo può comportare un incremento del contenuto di sostanza organica negli strati superficiali del suolo. Nell'esperimento di lungo periodo del lighthouse ha evidenziato un incremento di circa 1% in 10 anni rispetto ai suoli gestiti in convenzionale. Quest'ultima, infatti, determinando un ambiente più favorevole ai fenomeni ossidativi porta ad un impoverimento nel tempo della sostanza organica.

Raccomandazioni

Le lavorazioni conservative consentono di ridurre la mineralizzazione della sostanza organica, garantendo la conservazione del suolo, ma devono essere applicate in maniera da evitare un'eccessiva compattazione dei suoli con operazioni colturali intempestive e richiedono una gestione razionale dei residui colturali e delle erbe infestanti. Una gestione

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ottimale richiede una formazione continua e aggiornata e lo scambio di conoscenze, anche in riferimento alle opportunità di finanziamento.

Figura 1: Curve di compattazione del suolo associate a diverse lavorazioni del suolo.

Figura 2: Accumulo e consumo di sostanza organica nel suolo in funzione dell'aerazione nel suolo.

Practice Abstract #24

Conservation tillages and soil carbon

Authors: Gianluca Carboni ¹, Valentina Mereu ²

Objective

Soil health and fertility in the Mediterranean region are deteriorating due to increasingly unfavorable environmental conditions, including ongoing changes in climate conditions and more intense and frequent extreme events such as droughts, heatwaves, and floods. Conventional crop management involving deep and frequent tillage leads to a depletion of organic matter and carbon in the soil, resulting in reduced fertility and lower aggregate stability, which increases soil's susceptibility to erosion. Conservation tillage techniques can contribute to the mitigation of these effects by preserving water and soil. Conservation tillage seeks to minimize "soil disturbance." This, combined with "crop residue management," helps protect soil surface from erosion and increase its organic matter content over time.

Result

By reducing tillage and soil disturbance, soil becomes more compact and less oxygenated (Fig. 1), reducing the mineralization rate of organic matter (Fig. 2). This can lead to an increase of the organic matter content in the upper soil layers, as observed in the long-term experiment, lighthouse, that showed an increase of about 1% over 10 years compared to conventionally managed soils. In fact, conventional practices create an environment that favors oxidative processes, leading to a depletion of organic matter over time.

Recommendations

Conservation tillage allows for the reduction of organic matter mineralization while ensuring soil preservation. However, excessive soil compaction due to untimely agricultural operations must be prevented and a rational management of crop residues and weeds should be implemented. Moreover, optimal management requires continuous up-to-date training and knowledge exchange, including information on funding opportunities.

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— Conventional tillage
— Reduced tillage
— Sod seeding

Figure 1: Soil compaction curves based on different soil tillage.

Figure 2: Soil organic matter accumulation and consumption as a function of soil aeration.

Practice Abstract #25

Conservation Tillage and Soil Water Content

Authors: Gianluca Carboni ¹, Valentina Mereu ²

Objective

The fertility and productivity of crops in the Mediterranean region, especially rainfed cereal crops, are heavily dependent on rainfall, and environmental conditions are deteriorating due to ongoing climate change, characterized by more frequent and intense droughts and heatwaves. Conservation tillage helps with the preservation of water and soil, and is therefore considered a valid strategy for adapting to and mitigating climate change.

Result

The adoption of conservation tillage, especially sod seeding, enhances water retention in the soil during dry periods compared to conventional management, which tends to increase evaporation rates. This higher soil moisture content resulting from conservation tillage positively influences cereal crops throughout all stages of development. During the emergence phases, especially in dry falls, it fosters better conditions for seed germination and leads to more uniform crop emergence (Fig. 1). In addition, conservation tillage extends the crop growing cycle in late spring due to a higher water availability in the soil (Fig. 2) compared to conventional management.

Recommendations

Conservative soil management is an agronomic practice recommended especially where water resources are a limiting factor. However, it requires timely agricultural interventions to avoid excessive soil compaction. Moreover, optimal management requires continuous up-to-date training and knowledge exchange, including information on funding opportunities.

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VARIETY TRIAL SOD SEEDING

VARIETY TRIAL CONVENTIONAL

Figure 1: With sod seeding, wheat emergence is more uniform than with conventional management in dry Autumns.

Figure 2: The green colour of the plots managed with sod seeding highlights the higher water content during the month of May in the plots with sod seeding compared to those in conventional tillage.

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Practice Abstract #25

Lavorazioni conservative e contenuto d'acqua nel suolo

Autori: Gianluca Carboni ¹, Valentina Mereu ²

Obiettivo

La fertilità e la produttività della colture nell'area del Mediterraneo, soprattutto quelle cerealicole condotte in asciutto, è fortemente dipendente dalle piogge e le condizioni ambientali stanno peggiorando a causa dei cambiamenti climatici in corso con fenomeni siccitosi e ondate di calore più frequenti e di intensità maggiore. Le lavorazioni conservative aiutano la conservazione dell'acqua e del suolo e per questo sono considerate una valida strategia di adattamento e di contrasto ai cambiamenti climatici.

Risultato

L'adozione delle lavorazioni conservative e soprattutto della semina su sodo permette di conservare una maggiore quantità d'acqua nel suolo nei periodi siccitosi rispetto alla gestione convenzionale che favorisce l'evaporazione dell'acqua dal suolo. La conservazione dell'acqua promossa dalle lavorazioni conservative influisce positivamente sulle colture cerealicole in tutte le fasi di sviluppo. Durante le fasi di emergenza della coltura, in occasione di autunni poco piovosi, crea migliori condizioni per la germinazione dei semi e emergenze più regolari (fig. 1) rispetto alla gestione convenzionale che disseca il terreno più rapidamente, sia in tarda primavera allungando il ciclo produttivo grazie alla maggiore disponibilità di acqua nel suolo (fig. 2).

Raccomandazioni

La gestione conservativa del suolo è una pratica agronomica da raccomandare in quelle situazioni colturali in cui la risorsa idrica rappresenta un fattore limitante la produzione. Tuttavia, richiede tempestivi interventi colturali per evitare un'eccessiva compattazione dei suoli. Una gestione ottimale richiede una formazione continua e aggiornata e lo scambio di conoscenze, anche in riferimento alle opportunità di finanziamento.

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PROVA VARIETALE SEMINA SU SODO

PROVA VARIETALE IN CONVENZIONALE

Figure 1: Con la semina su sodo l'emergenza del grano è più uniforme rispetto alla gestione convenzionale in autunni siccitosi

Figure 2: Il colore verde delle parcelle gestite con semina su sodo evidenzia il maggior contenuto d'acqua durante il mese di maggio nelle parcelle con semina su sodo rispetto a quelle in convenzionale.

¹ Agricultural research agency of Sardinia (AGRIS)

² Euro Mediterranean Centre on Climate Change Foundation (CMCC)

Living Lab 2

Practice Abstract #26

Enhancing soil resilience and carbon sequestration through reduced tillage: a practical approach for farmers.

Author: Charles Rees ¹

Objective

The primary challenge addressed by the **practice of reduced tillage** is soil degradation caused by conventional farming methods, which often lead to erosion and loss of organic matter. This approach enables farmers to enhance the resilience of their soils and improve carbon sequestration, thereby contributing to the mitigation of climate change impacts. By reducing soil disturbance, farmers can preserve soil structure, increase water retention, and promote biodiversity in the soil ecosystem, ultimately leading to more sustainable agricultural practices.

Result

Implementing reduced tillage practices has shown promising results in enhancing soil health. Research indicates that reduced tillage increases the organic matter content of the soil, thereby improving its ability to store carbon. In the long term, this practice can lead to a significant increase in soil organic carbon (SOC) levels, which is essential for maintaining soil fertility and productivity. Additionally, reduced tillage has been linked to improved soil microbial activity and diversity, fostering a healthier soil ecosystem that supports crop growth and resilience against extreme weather events.

Recommendations

Farmers can adopt reduced tillage by modifying their planting and cultivation techniques to minimize soil disturbance. This requires using equipment designed for minimal tillage to different degrees, for example mulch tillage, strip tillage and zero tillage. The initial costs may include investment in specialized machinery or additional training, but adoption of these techniques can lead to numerous long-term benefits as well as labour and crop input savings. Additionally, farmers implementing these practices may be eligible for government incentives aimed at promoting sustainable agriculture, making this approach not only environmentally beneficial but also economically viable.

¹ The Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL)

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Practice Abstract #26

Verbesserung der Widerstandsfähigkeit des Bodens und der Kohlenstoffbindung durch reduzierte Bodenbearbeitung: ein praktischer Ansatz für Landwirte

Verfasser: Charles Rees ¹

Ziele

Die wichtigste Herausforderung, die mit der Praxis der reduzierten Bodenbearbeitung angegangen wird, ist die Verschlechterung der Böden durch konventionelle Anbaumethoden, die häufig zu Erosion und Verlust organischer Substanz führen. Dieser Ansatz ermöglicht es den Landwirten, die Widerstandsfähigkeit ihrer Böden zu erhöhen und die Kohlenstoffbindung zu verbessern und damit einen Beitrag zur Abschwächung der Auswirkungen des Klimawandels zu leisten. Durch die Verringerung der Bodenstörung können die Landwirte die Bodenstruktur erhalten, die Wasserrückhaltung verbessern und die Artenvielfalt im Bodenökosystem fördern, was letztlich zu nachhaltigeren landwirtschaftlichen Praktiken führt.

Ergebnisse

Die Anwendung reduzierter Bodenbearbeitungsmethoden hat vielversprechende Ergebnisse bei der Verbesserung der Bodengesundheit gezeigt. Forschungsergebnisse deuten darauf hin, dass eine reduzierte Bodenbearbeitung den Gehalt an organischer Substanz im Boden erhöht und damit seine Fähigkeit, Kohlenstoff zu speichern, verbessert. Langfristig kann diese Praxis zu einem erheblichen Anstieg des organischen Kohlenstoffgehalts im Boden führen, der für die Erhaltung der Bodenfruchtbarkeit und der Produktivität von entscheidender Bedeutung ist. Darüber hinaus wird die reduzierte Bodenbearbeitung mit einer verbesserten mikrobiellen Aktivität und Vielfalt im Boden in Verbindung gebracht, was ein gesünderes Bodenökosystem fördert, das das Pflanzenwachstum und die Widerstandsfähigkeit gegen extreme Wetterereignisse unterstützt.

¹ The Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL)

Empfehlungen

Landwirte können eine reduzierte Bodenbearbeitung anwenden, indem sie ihre Pflanz- und Anbautechniken so ändern, dass der Boden möglichst wenig gestört wird. Dies erfordert den Einsatz von Geräten, die in unterschiedlichem Maße für minimale Bodenbearbeitung ausgelegt sind, z. B. Mulch-, Streifen- und Null-Bodenbearbeitung. Zu den anfänglichen Kosten können Investitionen in Spezialmaschinen oder zusätzliche Schulungen gehören, aber die Einführung dieser Techniken kann zu zahlreichen langfristigen Vorteilen sowie zu Einsparungen bei Arbeitskräften und Betriebsmitteln führen. Darüber hinaus können Landwirte, die diese Praktiken anwenden, für staatliche Anreize zur Förderung einer nachhaltigen Landwirtschaft in Frage kommen, was diesen Ansatz nicht nur ökologisch vorteilhaft, sondern auch wirtschaftlich rentabel macht.

¹ The Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL)

Practice Abstract #27

Farm Soil Health Practice Adoption Benchmarking: Enabling Individual Performance Comparison

Author: Charles Rees ¹

Objective

As an addition to the economic assessment of the uptake of soil health management practices on Swiss arable farms a benchmarking app was developed. The objective of the application was to enable farmers to visualise the results of the survey and anonymously compare their answers to those of similar farmers. Additionally, through the app we shared additional resources so that farmers could access already available information leaflets and resources available on the topic of soil health.

Result

At the end of the survey campaign, 2'714 farmers completed our survey and of those, 2'001 requested the possibility to view the results of the survey and benchmark their performance. The app development took approximately 3 months and was shared with all farmers requesting access on 11th June 2024. Between mid-June and mid-August 2024 the app had been used for approximately 430 hours. The app was also presented to the Swiss Federal Office of Agriculture. The app received very good feedback from both the Farmers and Federal Office.

Recommendations

Benchmarking applications could prove to be a useful tool for self-motivating farmers to uptake, increase and improve the sustainability of their farming practices. Additionally, they provide a very convenient way to give back useful information to farmers who participate in research programmes, that enable them to make better decisions on their farms.

¹ The Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL)

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Practice Abstract #27

Benchmarking für die Einführung von Bodengesundheitspraktiken in landwirtschaftlichen Betrieben: Ermöglichung eines individuellen Leistungsvergleichs

Verfasser: Charles Rees ¹

Ziele

Als Ergänzung zur ökonomischen Bewertung der Anwendung von Bodenschutzmassnahmen auf Schweizer Ackerbaubetrieben wurde eine Benchmarking-App entwickelt. Das Ziel der App war es, den Landwirten die Möglichkeit zu geben, die Ergebnisse der Umfrage zu visualisieren und ihre Antworten mit denen ähnlicher Landwirte zu vergleichen. Darüber hinaus haben wir über die App zusätzliche Ressourcen zur Verfügung gestellt, so dass die Landwirte auf bereits verfügbare Informationsbroschüren und Ressourcen zum Thema Bodengesundheit zugreifen konnten.

Empfehlungen

Benchmarking-Anwendungen könnten sich als nützliches Instrument für Landwirte erweisen, die sich selbst motivieren, ihre landwirtschaftlichen Praktiken zu übernehmen, zu verbessern und nachhaltiger zu gestalten. Darüber hinaus bieten sie eine sehr bequeme Möglichkeit, Landwirten, die an Forschungsprogrammen teilnehmen, nützliche Informationen zur Verfügung zu stellen, die es ihnen ermöglichen, bessere Entscheidungen in ihren Betrieben zu treffen.

Ergebnisse

Am Ende der Umfragekampagne haben 2'714 Landwirt/innen unsere Umfrage ausgefüllt, von denen 2'001 die Möglichkeit wünschten, die Ergebnisse der Umfrage einzusehen und ihre Leistungen zu vergleichen. Die Entwicklung der App dauerte etwa drei Monate und wurde am 11. Juni 2024 allen Landwirt/innen, die einen Zugang beantragten, zur Verfügung gestellt. Zwischen Mitte Juni und Mitte August 2024 wurde die App während rund 430 Stunden genutzt. Die App wurde auch dem Schweizer Bundesamt für Landwirtschaft vorgestellt. Die App erhielt sowohl von den Landwirt/innen als auch vom Bundesamt ein sehr gutes Feedback.

¹ The Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL)

Practice Abstract #28

Undersowing

Author: Markus Steffens ¹

Objective

In the temperate latitudes of Europe, intensive agriculture with monocultures is often practised. Periods with little or no soil cover are still widespread. During these periods (e.g. winter fallow), soils are susceptible to wind and water erosion and nutrient loss. Many soils are also insufficiently covered during the main crop in spring and summer (e.g. in maize), which can lead to greater weed pressure, increased erosion in wet conditions and increased evaporation in dry conditions. In addition, the potential for nitrogen fixation in monocultures is not optimally utilised.

Recommendations

Many different undersown crops are available, consisting of one or a mixture of different species. The choice of undersow must be matched to the main and subsequent crop. A distinction must be made between freezing and overwintering mixtures or species. In addition, it must be determined whether the undersown crop is to follow a forage utilisation. Mixtures of different species are also available which, for example, have different root systems and can therefore develop the subsoil and improve its structure, repel pests and/or attract beneficial organisms, or increase nitrogen fixation and thus support the nutrient supply of the main and/or subsequent crop.

¹ The Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL)

Result

The use of undersown crops is a measure for continuous soil cover. This involves sowing an additional crop or mixture on a plot of land in addition to the main crop. Undersown crops can reduce the risk of erosion, improve soil structure, increase the input of organic matter into the soil, bind nutrients, support weed regulation, increase the biodiversity of a plot and reduce water evaporation in summer. Undersown crops can be cultivated as green manure and then worked into the soil after the main crop has been harvested. However, it can also be used as fodder and harvested at the appropriate time after the main crop has been harvested. If forage mixtures are cultivated as undersown crops, they can also suppress weeds such as thistles by being cut several times.

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Practice Abstract #28

Untersaaten

Verfasser: Markus Steffens ¹

Ziele

In den gemässigten Breiten Europas wird häufig eine intensive Landwirtschaft mit Monokulturen betrieben. Zeiträume ohne oder mit geringer Bodenbedeckung sind immer noch weit verbreitet. Während dieser Zeiträume (z.B. Winterbrache) sind die Böden anfällig für Wind- und Wassererosion und Nährstoffverluste. Auch während der Hauptkultur im Frühling und Sommer sind viele Böden unzureichend bedeckt (z.B. im Mais) wodurch ein grösserer Unkrautdruck entstehen, unter nassen Bedingungen verstärkt Erosion und unter trockenen Bedingungen verstärkte Verdunstung auftreten kann. Ausserdem wird das Potential der Stickstofffixierung in Monokulturen nicht optimal ausgenutzt.

Ergebnisse

Die Verwendung von Untersaaten ist eine Massnahme zur kontinuierlichen Bodenbedeckung. Dabei wird auf einer Parzelle zusätzlich zur Hauptkultur eine zusätzliche Kultur oder Mischung angesät. Untersaaten können das Erosionsrisiko reduzieren, die Bodenstruktur verbessern, den Eintrag organischer Substanz in den Boden steigern, Nährstoffe binden, die Unkrautregulation unterstützen, die Biodiversität einer Parzelle erhöhen und im Sommer die Verdunstung von Wasser reduzieren. Untersaat kann als Gründüngung angebaut und dann nach Ernte der Hauptfrucht in den Boden eingearbeitet werden. Sie kann jedoch auch als Futtermittel genutzt und nach der Ernte der Hauptfrucht zu gegebener Zeit geerntet werden. Werden Futtermischungen als Untersaaten angebaut, können diese durch die mehrmalige Schnittnutzung auch Beikräuter wie beispielsweise Disteln unterdrücken.

¹ The Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL)

Empfehlungen

Es sind viele unterschiedliche Untersaaten erhältlich, die sowohl aus einer wie auch aus einem Gemisch unterschiedlicher Arten bestehen. Die Wahl der Untersaat muss auf die Haupt- und Folgekultur abgestimmt sein. Es ist zu Unterscheiden zwischen abfrierenden und überwinternden Mischungen oder Arten. Ausserdem muss bei der Auswahl festgelegt werden, ob die Untersaat eine Futternutzung folgen soll. Es werden auch Gemische unterschiedlicher Arten angeboten, die z.B. unterschiedliche Wurzelsysteme aufweisen und somit den Unterboden erschliessen und dessen Struktur verbessern, Schädlinge abweisen und/oder Nützlinge anlocken, oder die Stickstofffixierung steigern und somit die Nährstoffversorgung der Haupt- und/oder Folgekultur unterstützen können.

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